

KYBERMEDIS WORKING PAPERS

No. 01 · May 2026

The Welfare State Matrix

An Architectural Diagnosis of the German Welfare State

Why reforms fail — and how structural clarification opens new scope for welfare-state reform

Prof. Dr. Udo Janßen, MD, MBA

KyberMedis GmbH, Berlin

Imprint and Bibliographic Information

Suggested Citation (APA)

Janßen, U. (2026). *The welfare state matrix: An architectural diagnosis of the German welfare state* (KyberMedis Working Papers No. 01). KyberMedis GmbH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20317879>

Published by

KyberMedis GmbH · Kolonnenstraße 8 · 10827 Berlin · www.kybermedis.de

Correspondence and Author

Prof. Dr. med. Udo Janßen · Managing Director, KyberMedis GmbH · udo.janssen@kybermedis.de · ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-6579-9645>

Licence

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0). The licence permits the sharing, adaptation and commercial use of the work, provided the author is credited. Licence text: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Version and Date

Version 1.0 · 21 May 2026

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20317879>

Series Note

The KyberMedis Working Papers present analytical studies of the structure and reform capacity of the German welfare state and its care systems. This paper is the English-language edition of a contribution published simultaneously in German as *Die Sozialstaats-Matrix* in the series *Beiträge zur Versorgungs- und Sozialstaatsarchitektur*.

Contents

Abstract	5
1 Introduction and Problem Definition	6
1.1 Reform Exhaustion as a Phenomenon	6
1.2 The Analytical Gap in Established Explanations	7
1.3 The Architectural Hypothesis as a Methodological Proposal.....	9
1.4 The Structure of the Paper	10
2 Methodological Self-Conception	11
2.1 The Methodology of Ideal Types after Weber	11
2.2 A Diagnostic Model, Not an Empirical Causal Model	11
2.3 Demarcation from the Welfare-Regime Typology	11
3 The Four Logics in Detail.....	13
3.1 Insurance — Collective, Contribution-Based.....	14
Definition and Constitutive Features	14
Historical Development in Germany	15
Current Manifestations	16
Structural Properties	16
Typical Pathologies of Conflation	16
3.2 Social Assistance — Individual, Tax-Based	17
Definition and Constitutive Features	17
Historical Development in Germany	17
Current Manifestations	18
Structural Properties	18
Typical Pathologies of Conflation	19
3.3 Public Provision — Collective, Tax-Based, Territorial.....	19
Definition and Constitutive Features	19
Historical Development in Germany	20
Current Manifestations	21
Structural Properties	21
Typical Pathologies of Conflation	22
3.4 Market — Individual, Premium-Based	23
Definition and Constitutive Features	23
Historical Development in Germany	24
Current Manifestations	24
Structural Properties	25
Typical Pathologies of Conflation	25
3.5 The Matrix in Overall View, and Pathologies of Conflation.....	26

4	Four Application Cases	27
4.1	Bürgergeld–GKV — The Insurance–Social Assistance Conflation	27
	Diagnosis of the Logic Break.....	27
	Previous Reform Attempts	28
	Sketch of an Architectural Clarification.....	29
	Expected Effects	29
4.2	Hospital Capacity Funding — The Insurance–Public Provision Conflation.....	30
	Diagnosis of the Logic Break.....	30
	Previous Reform Attempts	30
	Sketch of an Architectural Clarification.....	31
	Expected Effects	31
4.3	The PKV–GKV Interface — The Market–Insurance Conflation.....	32
	Diagnosis of the Logic Break.....	32
	Previous Reform Attempts	32
	Sketch of an Architectural Clarification.....	33
	Expected Effects	34
4.4	The Primary-Care Centre — All Four Logics at the Institutional Level	34
	Diagnosis of Conflation at the Institutional Level	34
	Previous Reform Attempts	35
	Sketch of an Architectural Clarification.....	35
	Expected Effects	36
5	Transition Path and Governance	37
5.1	Institutional Disentanglement as a Concept	37
5.2	A Welfare State Architecture Act	39
5.3	A Parallel Restructuring of the Social Code	40
5.4	International References: the Netherlands and Sweden	42
	The Dutch Model: Zvw, Wlz, Wmo.....	42
	The Swedish Model: Regional Tax Funding.....	43
6	Research Outlook and Follow-Up Questions.....	44
6.1	Methodological Development.....	44
6.2	Empirical Follow-Up Research	44
6.3	Political Follow-Up Questions.....	45
6.4	On Urgency: the Reform-Policy Implication of the Diagnosis	45
7	Eight Theses on the Architecture of the German Welfare State.....	47
	Bibliography.....	48
	Appendix A — Glossary of Key Terms	52
	Appendix B — About the Author.....	54

Abstract

Over the past three decades, the German welfare state has undergone more reforms than in the five decades before — and in the process has not stabilised but destabilised. This paper advances the thesis that the structural cause of recurrent reform crises lies not primarily in demography, scarcity of funding or a shortage of skilled personnel, but in the systematic conflation of four welfare-state logics: Insurance (collective, contribution-based), Social Assistance (individual, tax-based), Public Provision (collective, tax-based, territorially anchored) and Market (individual, premium-based).

The Welfare State Matrix develops an analytical diagnostic model — not an empirical causal model. Methodologically it follows the construction of ideal types in the Weberian sense (Weber, 1922) and makes visible where the effect of welfare-state reform is systematically absorbed by structural logic breaks. The analysis shows that exemplary fields of reform — the contribution-based health-insurance cover of recipients of Germany's means-tested minimum income support system (*Bürgergeld*), the capacity funding of hospitals, the interface between statutory and private health insurance, and the structures of primary care — display a consistent pathology: at each of these points incompatible logics meet without the conflation having been resolved in architectural terms. In the case of the primary-care centre this pathology appears in especially concentrated form — here all four logics converge at the level of a single care institution. Reform efforts fail less because of an absence of political will than because of this unresolved structural conflation.

International reference systems show that architectural clarification is not only practically feasible but leads to structurally more stable and demonstrably more capable care systems: the Netherlands, with the separation — established since 2006 — of the *Zorgverzekeringswet*, the *Wet langdurige zorg* and the *Wet maatschappelijke ondersteuning*, whose reformed system held leading positions in international performance comparisons for years; and the Swedish system, with its regional tax funding. The paper proposes a Welfare State Architecture Act on the model of regulatory framework legislation, a parallel restructuring of the Social Code (*Sozialgesetzbuch*) along the four logics, and a step-by-step clarification strategy directed at the most costly logic breaks. The Welfare State Matrix makes this architectural clarification possible; it is not itself a reform programme but supplies the hitherto unstated precondition for the success of any such programme.

Keywords: Welfare State Matrix, care architecture, architectural clarification, welfare state, ideal types, institutional disentanglement, welfare-state reform, health policy, health insurance, hospital funding, *Bürgergeld*, primary care

1 Introduction and Problem Definition

1.1 Reform Exhaustion as a Phenomenon

The German welfare state is in a condition of permanent reform. In the health-care sector alone, more than two dozen federal acts were passed between 1993 and 2025 — on the count of the Advisory Council on the Assessment of Developments in the Health Care System — each claiming to stabilise the system fundamentally or to realign it (Sachverständigenrat, 2023). In social insurance there followed the pension structure reform of 1992, the introduction of long-term care insurance in 1995, the Hartz Acts of 2003–2005, the Statutory Health Insurance Modernisation Act of 2003, the Statutory Health Insurance Care Provision Strengthening Act of 2015, the Long-Term Care Strengthening Acts I to III, the *Bürgergeld* Act of 2022/2023 and, most recently, the Hospital Care Improvement Act of 2024. This list could readily be doubled in length.

The plain empirical observation is this: over the past thirty years the welfare state has seen more reforms than in the fifty years before — and in the process has not stabilised but destabilised.

The hospital landscape is eroding: 56 per cent of German hospitals recorded an annual loss in 2024, 16 per cent were in the red zone of heightened insolvency risk, and average liquidity reserves at half of all hospitals now suffice for only two weeks (Augurzky, Krolop, Hollenbach, Monsees, Pilny & Wuckel, 2025).

Long-term care faces a structural problem of staffing and financing: the staffing-assessment procedure mandated by the federal legislator itself under § 113c of Social Code Book XI indicates an average additional personnel requirement of 36 per cent for residential long-term care — which further aggravates an already acute shortage of skilled staff — while the social long-term care insurance scheme operated with a structural deficit in 2023, and the planned contribution increase of 0.2 percentage points will at best suffice for a single budget year (Rothgang & Müller, 2024). Outpatient care in rural areas is becoming fragile (Schröter, 2024).

The average supplementary contribution rate in statutory health insurance has been rising for years with no discernible prospect of stabilisation: introduced in 2015 at a reference value of 0.9 per cent, it stood at 1.7 per cent in 2024. In 2025 it jumped to 2.5 per cent, the largest single increase since the indicator was introduced. For 2026 it was set by the Federal Ministry of Health at 2.9 per cent, on the recommendation of the GKV estimating panel of 15 October 2025; the total GKV contribution rate thereby reaches 17.5 per cent — its highest level since the introduction of social insurance (Bundesamt für Soziale Sicherung, 2025).

To this is added an unprecedented event: in September 2025 the National Association of Statutory Health Insurance Funds (GKV-Spitzenverband) resolved — as the first self-governing institution in the history of social insurance in the Federal Republic — to bring legal action against the Federal Republic of Germany, because the flat-rate contributions for recipients of *Bürgergeld* systematically fail to cover costs; the Higher Social Court of North Rhine-Westphalia has jurisdiction at first instance (GKV-Spitzenverband, 2025).

We therefore face a paradox: rarely before has so much been reformed, and rarely before has the result been so unsatisfactory. How is this to be explained?

1.2 The Analytical Gap in Established Explanations

The established explanations move along three familiar axes: demography, financing and personnel. Demographically, the picture is this: as the numerically large baby-boomer cohorts move into the age-associated high-risk phases of life, the prevalence of chronic illness and multimorbidity rises — with a progressively increasing burden of disease and correspondingly higher benefit expenditure in health and long-term care insurance over the coming two decades. At the same time, the shrinking working population reduces contributory income, so that the ratio between contributors and benefit recipients shifts structurally.

On the financing side, attention turns first to the growing federal subsidy requirement. The regular federal subsidy to the GKV has been fixed at 14.5 billion euros since 2017; its share of total GKV expenditure thereby fell from 9.2 per cent (2010) to around 4.6 per cent (2024). At the same time, total GKV expenditure reached a historic high of around 352 billion euros in 2025. This rise was driven primarily by growth in the hospital sector of 9.6 per cent — more than double the long-run average — and by the refinancing of the collective-pay increases of 2024 (Bundesministerium für Gesundheit, 2026a).

Added to this is the cost dynamic in pharmaceuticals. Net pharmaceutical expenditure in the GKV rose by 74 per cent between 2014 and 2023, to 54 billion euros, while the number of prescriptions increased by only 13.2 per cent over the same period. This rise is borne above all by patent-protected high-price products such as oncological agents, whose net cost stood at 10.6 billion euros in 2022; monoclonal antibodies alone generated 4.7 billion euros in turnover — at a prescription share for this high-price class of only 1.5 per cent (Schröder, 2024; Schwabe & Ludwig, 2023; WIdO, 2024).

A third problem is the investment weakness of the Länder with respect to hospitals: their funding, at 4.24 billion euros in 2024, covered only around 60 per cent of the substance-preserving investment requirement of roughly 7 billion euros — leaving an annual investment gap of around 40 per cent (Deutsche Krankenhausgesellschaft, 2025).

And finally, a reform of contribution assessment is not forthcoming: the Statutory Health Insurance Contribution Rate Stabilisation Act, adopted by the Federal Cabinet in April 2026, does provide for an extraordinary increase of the contribution assessment ceiling and the compulsory insurance threshold by 300 euros per month each, as well as limits on the contribution-free co-insurance of family members; it nonetheless remains within the existing architecture of the insurance system and does not resolve the fundamental question of a broader contribution base (Bundesministerium für Gesundheit, 2026b).

On the personnel axis, finally, stand the shortage of skilled staff, the migration into occupations not related to care (Hasselhorn, Müller & Tackenberg, 2005; Deutscher Berufsverband für Pflegeberufe, 2019) and demographically driven waves of retirement. Added to this is a historically high level of occupational dissatisfaction: the Marburger Bund documents in its most recent member survey that 28 per cent of salaried doctors are considering a change of profession and that almost half report frequent overwork (Marburger Bund, 2025).

All three axes of explanation are real, well documented and highly relevant politically — they form the backdrop of every serious debate on the welfare state and are systematised at a high level, time and

again, in the ongoing reports of the Advisory Council on the Assessment of Developments in the Health Care System and in the relevant textbook literature on social policy (M. G. Schmidt, 2005; Bäcker, Naegele & Bispinck, 2020). What they cannot explain is the specific persistence of reform exhaustion. For if it were solely a matter of demography, finance and personnel, one would expect reforms aimed precisely at those axes to take effect. Yet the accompanying research on the major reform projects of the past decade shows a consistently critical record — for instance in long-term care reform, whose effect is judged inadequate even after several Long-Term Care Strengthening Acts (Rothgang, 2023), or in the hospital reform efforts, which in the assessment of the relevant economic research have not so far decisively halted the structural dynamic of losses (Augurzky et al., 2025). Reforms are absorbed in the implementation process, diluted, reinterpreted against the original reform impulse, or counteracted by subsequent legislation.

The political scientist Wolfgang Streeck and the institutionalist school of comparative welfare-state research have coined the term “institutional drift” for such patterns (Streeck & Thelen, 2005): reforms are formally adopted, but their effect is consumed by unintended interactions with existing institutional structures. Hacker (2004), in an influential analysis of the United States welfare state, has shown that “risk shifts” between the insured, the state and the market are frequently produced not by visible reforms but by inconspicuous changes at interfaces — by what he calls “the hidden politics of social policy retrenchment”.

The thesis of this paper is this: German reform exhaustion can be reconstructed most precisely as an architectural problem. The system is not primarily under-financed, under-staffed or demographically overburdened — it is structurally ill-ordered. Four welfare-state logics that, in their ideal form, are clearly separable from one another have over decades been pushed into one another, layered upon one another and offset against one another. Every single reform of the past thirty years runs up, at this conflation, against limits of effectiveness that cannot be overcome by more money, more personnel or smarter management.

1.3 The Architectural Hypothesis as a Methodological Proposal

At the centre of this paper stands the Welfare State Matrix as an analytical tool. It orders welfare-state benefits along two dimensions: first, by their financing logic (contribution-based versus tax-based); second, by their mode of address (collective versus individual). From this two-dimensional arrangement four ideal types emerge:

- **Insurance** — collective, contribution-based. The principle of a solidarity-based risk community founded on acquired entitlements (statutory health insurance, statutory pension insurance, unemployment insurance, social long-term care insurance).
- **Social Assistance** — individual, tax-based. The principle of needs-oriented subsistence protection under the responsibility of the political community (*Bürgergeld*, social assistance, basic income support, training assistance, asylum seekers' benefits).
- **Public Provision** (*Daseinsvorsorge*) — collective, tax-based, territorial. The principle of the area-wide provision of vital infrastructures by territorial authorities, especially at the regional level (hospital planning, public transport, fire service).
- **Market** — individual, premium-based. The principle of equivalence-based, private-law risk cover in competition (private health insurance, private supplementary long-term care insurance, occupational disability insurance, occupational pension provision in the insurance model).

These four logics are analytically separable in their pure form — empirically they have long ceased to be separable in the German welfare state.

In the classical Bismarckian construction, up to the early post-war decades, the separation between contribution-financed insurance and tax-financed assistance was still institutionally largely preserved: the social insurance institutions operated as closed risk communities of gainfully employed members, while provision for those unable to work and the destitute was organised through municipally administered poor relief (Hockerts, 2011; Ritter, 2010).

With the pension reform of 1957 — the introduction of the pay-as-you-go method and of the dynamic pension under Adenauer — a first structural break set in, shifting society-wide solidarity elements into the insurance system (Hockerts, 2011; Schmähl, 2007). In what followed, several reform waves successively deepened confluences that are structurally effective in today's configuration. Of particular note are: the structural reforms of the 1970s; the introduction of long-term care insurance in 1995 as a hybrid construction between insurance and public provision; the Hartz reforms of 2003–2005, with the transfer of population groups not in employment into social insurance; the Pharmaceutical Market Reorganisation Act (AMNOG) of 2010; the Hospital Structure Act of 2015; and most recently the long-term-care-strengthening and *Bürgergeld* legislation.

At the points where logics are conflated, there arises what this paper terms a “logic break”: structures in which financing logic and responsibility logic do not match, so that steering, cost transparency and political accountability are systematically lost.

The central observation of the present study is that these logic breaks are not random by-products but form a pattern. They have arisen step by step over several decades, not through a single mistaken decision but through a multitude of individually plausible acts of political pragmatism. And they are — as this study seeks to show — the common ground at which the reform policy of recent decades meets its limit of effectiveness.

1.4 The Structure of the Paper

The paper is divided into four main parts. Chapter 2 sets out its methodological self-conception: the matrix is introduced as an ideal-typical diagnostic instrument after Weber (1922) and distinguished from an empirical causal model. Chapter 3 unfolds the four logics in detail — each with its definition, historical development, current manifestations, structural properties and typical pathologies of conflation. Chapter 4 applies the model to four cases: *Bürgergeld* health insurance, hospital capacity funding, the interface between statutory and private health insurance, and the primary-care centre, in which all four logics converge at the institutional level. Chapter 5 develops a transition path with a concrete governance proposal and international references. Chapter 6 formulates a research outlook and political follow-up questions. Chapter 7 draws the line of argument together, in conclusion, into eight theses.

The present paper understands itself as an analytical diagnosis of the German welfare state, not as a reform programme. It reconstructs the structural constellation at which the effectiveness of reform has been systematically absorbed over several decades, and in so doing poses a prior question that is structurally antecedent to any concrete reform policy. The analytical separation between architecture and reform is a constitutive component of the argument presented here: reform policy can build upon the architectural diagnosis, but it is not its result. This methodological distinction — architecture as the prior question, reform as the consequence — is systematically elaborated in the further course of the paper.

2 Methodological Self-Conception

2.1 The Methodology of Ideal Types after Weber

The Welfare State Matrix is an ideal-typical construct in the sense of the methodology developed by Max Weber (1922). Ideal types, as Weber precisely puts it, are not empirical descriptions of an encountered reality but mental intensifications of certain elements of reality into an internally consistent construct. Their function is not depictive but heuristic: they make the distinctiveness of concrete social phenomena recognisable through comparison with the ideal type.

Transferred to the undertaking pursued here, this means: the four logics — Insurance, Social Assistance, Public Provision and Market — exist nowhere in the German welfare state in this pure form. Statutory health insurance is not pure insurance — it contains massive elements of social assistance (such as the contribution-free co-insurance of family members, the compulsory insurance of recipients of *Bürgergeld*, the assumption of pregnancy and childbirth benefits for non-employed co-insured persons). Hospital financing is not pure public provision — since the dual financing of 1972 it has been structurally split between insurance logic (the DRG system for operating costs) and public provision (investment financing by the Länder). Analogous hybrid constructions can be identified in every other field of social benefits.

Ideal-typical modelling serves precisely to make this empirical conflation visible. The question is not: which logic does this phenomenon correspond to? — for the answer is mostly: several at once. The question is rather: which components can be identified, and to which logic does each component belong? The matrix decomposes; it does not necessarily classify.

2.2 A Diagnostic Model, Not an Empirical Causal Model

A second methodological clarification is necessary: the Welfare State Matrix does not claim to be an empirical causal model in the sense of quantitative political science or health economics. It does not assert that the success of a welfare-state reform could be predicted by a regression analysis from the degree of logic conflation. Such an operationalisation would not only be empirically demanding — it would overextend the reach of the model.

What the matrix achieves is something else: it provides a diagnostic scheme with which concrete reform constellations can be reconstructed and analysed for structural tensions. The model is falsified not by a missing statistical correlation but by a better alternative reconstruction of a concrete case. This methodology is well anchored in the historical-institutionalist tradition of political science (Streeck & Thelen, 2005) and in health services research. It is not a weaker science but a different one — one that takes the distinctiveness of institutional constellations seriously and does not force it into standardised variables.

2.3 Demarcation from the Welfare-Regime Typology

The matrix proposed here stands in productive tension with the most frequently cited typology of welfare-state research worldwide, the three-worlds classification of Gøsta Esping-Andersen (1990). Esping-Andersen distinguishes liberal (the USA, the United Kingdom), conservative-corporatist (Germany, France, Italy) and social-democratic (Sweden, Denmark, Norway) welfare regimes — a

typology that has since been replicated, criticised and extended in countless studies (cf. Lessenich, 2012).

Esping-Andersen's classification is an external typology: it orders nation states in comparative perspective. The Welfare State Matrix proposed here is an internal diagnostic: it orders components within a single welfare regime — the German conservative-corporatist one — along their immanent logic characteristics. The two tools therefore do not compete; they operate at different levels of analysis.

What the matrix accomplishes in this reading is an intra-architectural analysis of the German welfare regime. It makes it explicable why such different levels of performance arise even within the conservative-corporatist ideal type — for instance between the comparatively logic-pure accident insurance scheme (a clear insured event, clear institutional responsibility, little conflation) and the highly hybrid hospital financing with its dual financing structure since 1972. Both belong to the same welfare regime. But they have very different logic architectures — and correspondingly different vulnerabilities to demographic, fiscal and political strains.

A third methodological point of connection lies in health services research. The Advisory Council, in its reports of 2018 and 2023, has repeatedly pointed to structural breaks in the German care system — between outpatient and inpatient care, between the health and long-term care systems, between the logic of care and the logic of assistance (Sachverständigenrat, 2018, 2023). The Welfare State Matrix generalises these observations and integrates them into a unified analytical framework. The accompanying research on the major reform projects of recent years — the Long-Term Care Strengthening Acts, the hospital structure reforms, the Federal Participation Act, the Statutory Health Insurance Care Provision Strengthening Act — offers a rich empirical illustration on which the paper draws in what follows.

3 The Four Logics in Detail

This chapter unfolds the four welfare-state logics in ideal-typical clarity. Each logic is presented along a uniform sub-structure: constitutive features, historical development in Germany, current manifestations, structural properties and typical pathologies of conflation. Figure 1 presents the matrix in synoptic form.

Figure 1: The Welfare State Matrix in ideal-typical form (author's own illustration)

Table 1 complements this ideal-typical overview with the institutional dimension — it assigns to each of the four logics its responsible bodies, its form of supervision and governance, and its legal anchoring in the German welfare state.

Feature	Insurance	Social Assistance	Public Provision	Market
Responsible bodies	Self-governing public-law corporations (social insurance institutions)	Federal government (<i>Bürgergeld</i> , asylum); Länder and municipalities (social assistance, integration support)	Länder and municipal authorities (hospital planning, public transport, educational infrastructure)	Private-law insurance undertakings (public limited companies, mutual insurance associations / VVaG)
Supervision and governance	Subsidiary state supervision (BAS, BMAS, BMG); jointly staffed self-governing bodies	Parliamentary mandate; municipal self-government within a federal statutory framework	Needs planning by the Länder; municipal authority over sites and ownership	BaFin (insurance supervision under the VAG); competition-law oversight
Legal basis	Social Code Books IV, V, VI, VII, XI; Art. 87(2) Basic Law; the welfare-state principle (Arts. 20, 28 Basic Law)	Social Code Books II, IX, XII; Asylum Seekers' Benefits Act (AsylbLG); Federal Training Assistance Act (BAföG); municipal-law provisions	Hospital Financing Act (KHG) and Länder hospital acts; the doctrine of public provision (Forsthoff, 1938)	Insurance Contract Act (VVG), Insurance Supervision Act (VAG); insurance contract law; PKV regulation

Table 1: *Responsible bodies and governance of the four logics in the German welfare state (author's own illustration)*

The following sections work out the four logics individually. The emphasis in each case lies on the internal consistency of the logic concerned, its historical anchoring in the German welfare state, and the typical pathologies that arise when the logic is conflated with others.

3.1 Insurance — Collective, Contribution-Based

Definition and Constitutive Features

The insurance logic of the German welfare state organises a public-law, solidarity-based compulsory community whose benefits are granted on the basis of acquired entitlements. It is to be distinguished, constitutively, from private-law insurance in competition — including the mutual insurance association (VVaG), which likewise rests on an idea of pooling but operates as a private-law, contractually constituted risk community with individual premium calculation. Social insurance, by contrast, is configured as a public-law corporation with constitutional rank (Art. 87(2) of the Basic Law for the federally administered institutions; the basic welfare-state duty arising from Arts. 20(1) and 28(1) of the Basic Law); its membership rests on statutory compulsory insurance, not on contract.

The constitutive features of the insurance logic are: first, contribution financing through insurable income; second, the capacity principle of contribution assessment — contributions are assessed by individual capacity to pay, not by individual risk, with the contribution assessment ceiling as the upper threshold; third, self-governance as the organisational form (with institutional autonomy, jointly staffed self-governing bodies and subsidiary state supervision); fourth, neutrality of burden with respect to extraneous tasks — social insurance ideally bears only those burdens that correspond to its insured subject matter, while extraneous tasks are to be refinanced from general budget funds. This fourth feature is not codified as an explicit legal rule; it follows from the equivalence character of contribution financing and finds its practical — though, in scope and assessment, contested — recognition in the federal subsidy for the discharge of non-insurance benefits (§ 221 of Social Code Book V).

Solidarity-based social insurance thereby demarcates itself in two directions. As against the logic of social assistance, it remains insurance-typical in the sense that benefits are granted not on the basis of a means test but on the basis of an insured event having occurred where an entitlement exists. As against the market logic, by contrast, it is solidarity-based: benefits are not calculated on the basis of an individual risk assessment but are borne evenly within the risk community — contributions are assessed on income, benefits on need. In this twofold demarcation — no means-testing principle, no risk selection — lies the specific architecture of German social insurance; in it, it differs at the same time from the pure equivalence principle of private-sector insurance, which is to be discussed under the market logic (Section 3.4).

Historical Development in Germany

German social insurance arose between 1883 and 1889, under the Bismarck government, as an answer to the social question of the industrial working class. The Act concerning the Health Insurance of Workers of 1883 established for the first time a state-framed, jointly financed and self-governing insurance structure (Ritter, 2010; Tennstedt, 1981). There followed accident insurance in 1884, invalidity and old-age insurance in 1889, salaried-employees' insurance in 1911, unemployment insurance in 1927 and — much later — social long-term care insurance in 1995.

Bismarck's system was marked by a twofold clarity: first, it was an insurance system for dependent employees and their families, not a universal citizens' insurance system; and second, it organised itself along occupational-estate lines — local sickness funds, company sickness funds, guild sickness funds, substitute funds for salaried employees (Hockerts, 1980). This structural clarity was, for more than a century, the strength of the German model: there was a clear separation between what was organised through social insurance (insured events for the insured) and what counted as the assistance task of the political community (subsistence protection for the destitute, financed through municipal poor relief and — beginning with Reich welfare provision from 1924, and systematically from the Federal Social Assistance Act of 1961 — through federally framed tax funds). This dividing line between contribution-financed insurance and tax-financed assistance is well documented in welfare-state research (Sachße & Tennstedt, 1980; Ritter, 2010). In the core area of health insurance it even remained largely intact until 2003: only with the Statutory Health Insurance Modernisation Act (Federal Law Gazette [BGBl.] I 2003, p. 2190) was a federal subsidy for the discharge of non-insurance benefits introduced at all, institutionalised for the long term from 2007 with the Statutory Health Insurance Competition Strengthening Act (Pressel, 2012; Bundesrechnungshof, 2021).

Over the past three decades this structural clarity has gradually waned. Several waves of legislation have shifted tasks of state assistance into the contribution financing of social insurance, without this being openly identified as a paradigm shift in social policy — a finding that is systematically documented in the relevant welfare-state research (Hockerts, 2011; Lessenich, 2012; M. G. Schmidt, 2005). The best-known instance is the health insurance of recipients of unemployment benefit II, or *Bürgergeld*, which is addressed in detail in Chapter 4. The structural observation here is this: the assistance task was not abolished but shifted from the federal budget into the GKV contribution pool — and at a flat-rate contribution that has for years systematically fallen short of the actual costs of care. The IGES Institute has quantified the extent twice: for 2016 the flat-rate contribution actually paid stood at 90.36 euros, whereas a cost-covering rate would have been 275.31 euros (a coverage

ratio of 38 per cent); for 2022, 108.48 euros stood against a cost-covering flat rate of 311.45 euros (a coverage ratio of 39 per cent), corresponding to an annual shortfall of 9.2 billion euros (IGES Institut, 2024). The updated figures for 2024 (119.60 euros actually paid) and 2026 (144.04 euros) attest to the persistence of the structural gap.

Current Manifestations

The central bearers of the insurance logic in today's German welfare state are the five branches of social insurance: statutory health insurance, statutory pension insurance, unemployment insurance, statutory accident insurance and social long-term care insurance. They cover the overwhelming majority of the population, finance themselves primarily from jointly paid contributions and are organised as self-governing public-law corporations.

Within the insurance logic there are clearly non-insurance functions — such as the contribution-free co-insurance of family members, maternity and pregnancy benefits, and the assumption of contributions for recipients of certain social benefits. These functions are not located there out of an inner necessity of the insurance logic but have been attached to it step by step through political decisions — mostly because social insurance, as an already existing and capable infrastructure, offered the administratively most convenient solution. They have been the subject of political discussion for decades (cf. Wasem, 1996; Hockerts, 2011). That discussion, however, has always remained confined to adjusting the level and modalities of the federal subsidies to the GKV — the structural question of whether these functions belong in the insurance logic at all has never been seriously posed.

Structural Properties

The insurance logic is intrinsically robust against cyclical fluctuations — demographic pressure is certainly perceptible, but the principle of the risk community holds even in ageing societies, provided that the rules of contribution assessment and entitlement are adjusted accordingly. It is difficult to reform, because every reform touches entitlement rights and is thereby bound by constitutional law (Art. 14 of the Basic Law, the guarantee of property) (Bundesverfassungsgericht, 2009). It is strong in steering its core task (collective risk cover) but weak in steering with respect to non-insurance functions — for there both the democratic mandate is lacking (self-governance represents the contributors, not the general public) and fiscal clarity is lacking (contribution pools are not budget items under parliamentary control).

Typical Pathologies of Conflation

The central pathology of the insurance logic in the German welfare state is the gradual shifting of assistance and public-provision tasks into the contribution pool. This shift occurs not through a single political decision but through a multitude of pragmatically motivated individual steps: through the assumption of flat-rate contributions for recipients of social benefits, through the loading of social insurance with society-wide tasks (such as the resettler pensions or the East German Pension Transition Act), through the de facto cross-financing of the investment funding gap in hospitals, which under the constitution is a task of the Länder (§ 9 of the Hospital Financing Act).

While the substance-preserving investment requirement is put at around 7 billion euros per year nationwide, on the concurring calculation of the joint self-governing bodies (DKG, GKV-Spitzenverband, PKV), the Länder most recently provided only 4.24 billion euros in KHG funding (2024);

the share of hospital investment in gross domestic product fell from 0.23 per cent (1991) to 0.09 per cent (2024) and thus stands at only around 40 per cent of the initial value (Deutsche Krankenhausgesellschaft, 2025; GKV-Spitzenverband, DKG & PKV, 2024). The gap is in effect cross-financed through the DRG revenues from operating costs — that is, from the contribution pool of the insured.

What all these shifting steps have in common is this: each is individually rational, and each shifts the burden of conflict into the opaque contribution relationships of social insurance. In doing so they relieve, in differing ways, both the federal budget and the Länder budgets:

The federal government saves visible expenditure items where tasks migrate into the contribution pool — for instance in the flat-rate contributions for recipients of *Bürgergeld*, in the non-insurance benefits of the GKV (pregnancy, maternity, contribution-free co-insurance of family members), or in the tasks of the public health service, which are increasingly co-financed by the joint self-governing bodies.

The Länder, for their part, relieve their budgets through the continuous reduction of their KHG investment funds, the difference being one that hospitals must compensate through GKV operating funds — and through the depletion of substance in the public health service, whose structural gap is now likewise supported by GKV funds under the “Pact for the Public Health Service” (Kuhn & Wildner, 2020; Bundesrechnungshof, 2023). The result is a contribution pool that increasingly becomes a shadow treasury of state public provision — politically attractive for both federal levels, politically untenable for the contributors.

3.2 Social Assistance — Individual, Tax-Based

Definition and Constitutive Features

The logic of social assistance organises needs-oriented subsistence protection under the responsibility of the political community. Its constitutive features are: first, the means test as the precondition of granting a benefit — assistance is granted because, and to the extent that, a situation of hardship exists; second, tax financing from general budget funds; third, municipal or federal responsibility as the responsible body; fourth, the parliamentary mandate as the democratic foundation.

Assistance in this sense is constitutively distinct from insurance: it knows no entitlement, only need; it is financed not from contributions but from taxes; it is borne not by a risk community but by the general public as the democratic sovereign. This is more than a technical distinction — it is a normative architectural decision about what society organises as a communal task and what as a corporative one.

Historical Development in Germany

The German tradition of social assistance has several historical roots, well documented in welfare-state research (Sachße & Tennstedt, 1980; Ritter, 2010).

First, municipal poor relief, which found its formative organisational shape in the Elberfeld system from 1853: voluntary poor-relief officers, small-scale districts, individual assessment of need, municipal responsibility. The Elberfeld system became a model for numerous German cities and shaped the idea that assistance is a task of the political community.

Second, the Christian-charitable tradition — Diakonie, Caritas and the independent welfare associations became important bearers of practical assistance work, with considerable organisational and ideological autonomy.

Third, the social-democratic, labour-movement root, which in the Weimar Republic contributed substantially to anchoring assistance as a civil right and prepared the Reich Welfare Duty Act of 1924.

These three roots merged, in the further course of history, into the dual institutional structure of German welfare provision: municipal social welfare offices on the one side, independent welfare associations with a subsidiarity priority on the other. The Federal Social Assistance Act of 1961 codified this structure in a coherent body of legislation. In the late 1990s and early 2000s the system was fundamentally rebuilt twice: first through the introduction of basic income support in old age (2003), then through Social Code Book II (Hartz IV, 2005), which merged the previous unemployment assistance and the social assistance for persons capable of work into a single tax-financed assistance benefit. In 2023 Hartz IV was replaced by *Bürgergeld* — a reform that readjusted benefit levels, sanction rules and placement obligations in several steps but retained the structural architecture:

Bürgergeld is assistance in its ideal type — tax-financed, means-tested, parliamentarily mandated.

An important structural observation: while the assistance benefit *Bürgergeld* itself remains cleanly located within the assistance logic, the health insurance associated with it is incorporated into the insurance logic of the GKV. This allocation is no law of nature but the contingent result of a pragmatic decision: when the health insurance of those in need of assistance had to be regulated, the legislator fell back on the existing GKV infrastructure rather than building a separate, tax-financed protection system. What began historically as administrative simplification is today a structural conflation of logics — and precisely because it rests on a political decision and not on a necessity of the matter, it can also be corrected again. This asymmetry is elaborated in Chapter 4 as a central case of the architectural diagnosis.

Current Manifestations

The central manifestations of the assistance logic today are: *Bürgergeld* under Social Code Book II for those capable of work and in need of assistance; social assistance under Social Code Book XII for those not capable of work and in need of assistance; basic income support in old age and in the event of reduced earning capacity; the Federal Training Assistance Act (BAföG); the Asylum Seekers' Benefits Act; and integration support for people with disabilities under Social Code Book IX. To these are added municipal benefits — housing benefit, the education and participation package, municipal social work.

Structural Properties

In its core properties the assistance logic is the institutional counterpart of the insurance logic. It is highly responsive democratically — levels, conditions and eligibility rules are negotiated in parliament and can be adjusted within constitutional limits (the case law of the Federal Constitutional Court on the subsistence minimum). It is fiscally transparent, because it is financed from budget funds and appears as an expenditure item in the federal or Länder budget. It is administratively demanding, because the means test in the individual case requires a considerable administrative procedure. And it is normatively exposed, because it touches directly on the question of what the political community defines as the minimum standard of subsistence protection.

It is precisely this normative exposure that makes the assistance logic structurally susceptible to political cycles. Its benefit levels, eligibility conditions and access rules are renegotiated in recurring debates — from the *Bürgergeld* reform through the periodic adjustment of standard needs to the changes in jurisdiction and benefits for refugees, such as the change of legal regime in 2025 moving Ukrainian persons seeking protection from *Bürgergeld* back to the Asylum Seekers' Benefits Act. This is no defect of the assistance logic but an expression of its democratic constitution: unlike the entitlement-based insurance benefit, the assistance benefit stands constitutively under a reservation of parliamentary discretion. Architecturally, two points follow from this — first, that this political negotiability is an essential feature of the logic and not a deficiency to be remedied; and second, that it makes the assistance logic less predictable than the insurance logic, which is why a conflation of the two logics damages the reliability of the insurance side.

Typical Pathologies of Conflation

The typical pathology of conflation in the assistance logic lies in two directions: first, in its shift into the insurance logic (see above: *Bürgergeld* and the GKV as the prime example), and second, in its conflation with public provision at the municipal level. If, for instance, municipal social work is organised not as a budget-financed mandatory task but in effect remains a “voluntary benefit” that can be cut depending on the budgetary situation, then the assistance logic loses its constitutive reliability. The empirical constellation that forces this conflation is well documented: the Municipal Finance Report 2025 of the Bertelsmann Stiftung records, for the 2024 budget year, the largest municipal deficit in the history of the Federal Republic; municipal social expenditure rose within two years by around 25 per cent to 85 billion euros, integration support grew by 11.2 per cent in 2025 alone, and child and youth welfare by around 8.8 per cent annually (Geißler & Freier, 2025). Since 2014 municipal social expenditure has doubled; its share of total municipal expenditure now stands at 38 per cent. The principle of connexity anchored in federal law — whereby the party that occasions a task pays for it — is in practice not observed; mandatory tasks transferred by federal law are imposed on municipalities without full counter-financing, with the result that the already narrow scope for voluntary benefits — advice centres, municipal social work beyond the mandatory minimum, preventive structures — is in many places reduced to zero (Geißler & Freier, 2025). The result: the assistance logic degenerates, at the municipal level, into a subjunctive — if the Land or the municipality can and will, then help is given. This conflation weakens the assistance logic in its core content — the reliability of state responsibility.

3.3 Public Provision — Collective, Tax-Based, Territorial

Definition and Constitutive Features

The logic of public provision organises the area-wide provision of vital infrastructures by territorial authorities. Its constitutive features are: first, territorial anchoring — public provision is not person-related but space-related; second, tax financing from general budget funds; third, collective address — the service is made available to all inhabitants of a territory, irrespective of individual need or insurance entitlement; fourth, federal responsibility, which in Germany regularly lies with the Länder or the municipalities.

The concept of public provision (*Daseinsvorsorge*) was decisively coined by Ernst Forsthoff in the work *The Administration as a Provider of Services* (1938) and in his later writings on the “providing

administration” (Forsthoff, 1938). Forsthoff observed that modern industrial society had brought forth a new kind of state task: no longer the ordering and rule-setting administration, but the provision of those infrastructures without which individual existence in industrial society would be impossible. Transport, energy, water, education, area-wide health care — all of these are infrastructures whose provision the individual citizen cannot secure independently.

Historical Development in Germany

Municipal public provision in the narrower sense has its roots in the nineteenth century, when German cities, in the course of industrialisation, built waterworks, gasworks, slaughterhouses, hospitals and tramways — typically as municipal enterprises or as municipally owned companies. The federal character of the German state anchored public provision in a dual structure: the Länder are responsible for the overarching infrastructures (hospital planning, universities, regional transport infrastructure), the municipalities for the locally proximate services (schools, public local transport, water supply, local health structures).

Hospital planning has been the formative example of health-related public provision in Germany since the Hospital Financing Act (KHG) of 1972. The KHG established dual financing: the Länder finance investments (public provision), the sickness funds finance operating costs (insurance). This construction was conceived as a clean separation — it has, over the decades, become one of the most prominent pathologies of conflation in the German welfare state, because the Länder systematically no longer meet their investment responsibility under § 9 of the KHG and the missing investment funds are now in effect compensated from GKV contribution financing.

The data are unambiguous: the substance-preserving investment requirement of German hospitals amounts, on concurring calculations of the joint self-governing bodies, to around 7 billion euros per year (BVMed, 2023; Deutsche Krankenhausgesellschaft, 2025). The Länder’s KHG funding stood at 4.24 billion euros in 2024 and thereby covered only around 60 per cent of the requirement; an investment gap of around 40 per cent remained. For the reporting year 2023 the DKG had put the financing gap at 2.64 billion euros, corresponding to a shortfall of 41 per cent. In nominal terms, the KHG funding stood at 3.64 billion euros in 1991 and 3.29 billion euros in 2021 — adjusted for inflation, this corresponds to a loss of value of around 39.5 per cent against 1991. The accumulated investment backlog is put, depending on the calculation method, at around 50 billion euros (BVMed, 2023; Augurzky et al., 2025). The gap is in effect cross-financed through the DRG revenues from operating costs — that is, from the contribution pool of the insured — a conflation that is analysed in detail in Chapter 4.

Since the 1990s, public provision has moreover come under the pressure of the European competition order. The German concept of *Daseinsvorsorge* — developed by Ernst Forsthoff (1938) — has no direct equivalent in European primary law; the European Union works instead with the categories of “services of general interest” (SGI) and, more narrowly, “services of general economic interest” (SGEI).

With the Treaty of Lisbon (2009), Art. 14 TFEU (formerly Art. 16 TEC) was substantively extended; a Protocol No. 26 on services of general interest was added, recognising the autonomy of national bodies, the diversity of services and universal access as European values. At the same time, access to SGEI was elevated to the rank of primary law through Art. 36 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (Stelkens, 2021).

The member states decide largely autonomously on the definition, organisation and financing of their SGEI — though subject to the EU competition rules. SGEI are in principle subject to Art. 102 TFEU (market dominance) and to the state-aid law of Arts. 107 et seq. TFEU. Compensation payments for SGEI are, under the Altmark Trans case law of the European Court of Justice (ECJ; judgment C-280/00 of 24 July 2003), not relevant as state aid only if four cumulative conditions are met: a clear definition of public-service obligations, an objective and transparent setting of parameters, a limitation to the actual additional costs, and — in the absence of a tender — a comparison with an efficiently run average undertaking (EuGH, 2003; Europäische Kommission, 2011).

This case law has narrowed the scope of municipal and state responsibility and, in combination with the sectoral liberalisation directives — telecommunications in the 1990s, postal services in 1997, energy from 1998 onwards, rail from 2001 onwards — generated a persistent pressure of privatisation and liberalisation that has weakened public and municipal ownership in many fields (Stelkens, 2021). In health care, this pressure shows itself among other things in the state-aid discussion around municipal hospitals, in the awarding of emergency-rescue services and in the tendering obligation for public local transport services.

Current Manifestations

The central manifestations of public provision in the German health and social system are: hospital planning by the Länder; the responsibility for securing outpatient medical care (which formally lies with the Associations of Statutory Health Insurance Physicians but materially has the character of public provision); municipal health care — the public health service, advice centres, addiction support, health promotion; public local transport and its connection to the reachability of medical services across the territory; and — very weakly developed in Germany — the municipal responsibility for low-threshold care structures such as primary-care centres or social housing for the elderly.

Structural Properties

Public provision is the institutionally weakest of the four logics in the German welfare state. It has no responsible organisation of its own of the stature of social insurance; it is distributed across federal levels, each of which pursues its own fiscal interests; it is cut, in budgetary policy, wherever current crises lay claim to funds — this can be traced empirically in the consolidation phase of the early 2000s, in the municipal investment restraint that set in after the 2008 financial crisis, and in the renewed rise of municipal deficits from 2024, in which the municipal scope for investment is consumed by mandatory tasks and inflation (Geißler & Freier, 2025). And it is barely anchored normatively: the concept of *Daseinsvorsorge* has been established in constitutional and administrative-law scholarship since Forsthoff (1938) but is barely present in everyday political language — in contrast, for instance, to the French concept of the “service public”, which there exerts a considerable normative force.

The result: public provision has been quietly eroding for decades, without the structural erosion being articulated politically. The statistical evidence is overwhelming:

The number of hospitals in Germany fell from 2,411 (1991) to 1,874 (2024), the number of beds from 665,565 to 472,851 — a decline of around 22 and 29 per cent respectively; the number of public hospitals fell by 58.74 per cent since 1991, while the number of private hospitals grew by 63.69 per

cent; the share of private ownership rose from 22 per cent (2000) to around 40 per cent (2024) (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2024).

The public health service lost around 30 per cent of its staff in the 1990s; in 2020 only 407 specialists in public health worked in the 380 German public health offices — statistically barely one person per office — of whom almost half were aged 60 or older (Kuhn & Wildner, 2020). The Pact for the Public Health Service of 29 September 2020 provided 4 billion euros in federal funds for the period 2021 to 2026 and envisaged the creation of 5,000 new posts; follow-on financing beyond 2026 is not secured. The Federal Court of Audit, moreover, pointed out in its advisory report of 2023 that under the Basic Law the Länder and municipalities alone are responsible for the tasks and financing of the public health service, and that the federal government must refer the Länder to their own responsibility for the personnel costs of the public health service (Bundesrechnungshof, 2023). To this is added the already discussed investment gap in hospital financing, as well as the thinning of municipal advice structures — addiction support, debt counselling, family education — which, under the consolidation pressure of the past two decades, have in many places been scaled back to the statutory minimum (Geißler & Freier, 2025).

Typical Pathologies of Conflation

The typical pathology of public provision is its shift into the insurance logic. It shows itself paradigmatically in the hospital sector: when the Länder do not meet their investment responsibility under § 9 of the KHG — by carrying forward, over decades, KHG block funding and individual-project funding below the substance-preserving requirement — hospitals must cross-finance the uncovered investments from the DRG operating funds; in effect, public-provision responsibility thereby migrates into the contribution pool of the insured (Deutsche Krankenhausgesellschaft, 2025; Augurzky et al., 2025). When municipalities scale back their addiction support, pregnancy counselling or debt counselling under consolidation pressure, office-based doctors and hospitals take on tasks that do not belong to their insurance mandate — here too, public-provision responsibility migrates into social insurance.

In the outpatient sector, the pathology presents itself architecturally differently and requires a precise allocation of responsibilities. The mandate to secure outpatient contract-physician, psychotherapeutic and dental care lies, under § 75(1) of Social Code Book V, with the seventeen Associations of Statutory Health Insurance Physicians and the National Association of Statutory Health Insurance Physicians, organised as public-law corporations — not with the Länder. In this sector, the Länder are responsible not for the mandate to secure care itself but for hospital planning, the framework conditions of needs planning, individual structural-policy support programmes (establishment incentives in under-served areas, rural-doctor quotas in the licensing regulations), the responsibility for the public health service and supplementary municipal care structures.

When the Associations of Statutory Health Insurance Physicians reach structural limits in securing care in rural areas — a shortage of successors in general-practitioner care, disparities in remuneration between town and country, single-doctor practices no longer viable in business terms — and at the same time the Länder and municipalities do not actively shape the supplementary public-provision functions (public ownership, municipal medical care centres, primary-care centres), then investor-led medical care centres (iMVZ) enter the supply of care. These structures are not “private-sector” in the

sense of care outside the GKV system — they are fully integrated into the contract-physician care system via licences from the Associations of Statutory Health Insurance Physicians, are subject to their remuneration rules and are to that extent themselves part of the care that those associations are obliged to secure.

The structural finding, however, is a different one: according to data from the National Association of Statutory Health Insurance Dentists, iMVZ are concentrated to around 80 per cent in affluent large cities and contribute hardly at all to care in structurally weak rural areas (KZBV, 2024). Nationwide, private-equity firms operate, according to a study by Scheuplein (2024), at least 54 practice chains with around 50,000 employees at some 2,000 sites, above all in scalable specialist fields — ophthalmology, pathology, radiology, dentistry, dialysis. Since the Statutory Health Insurance Care Provision Strengthening Act of 2015 opened up the possibility of same-specialty MVZ formations, the spread of these structures has accelerated considerably. In 2023 the Länder of Bavaria, Rhineland-Palatinate and Schleswig-Holstein introduced a motion for a resolution in the Bundesrat providing for transparency registers, spatial limits on hospitals' power to establish such centres, and maximum care shares; the German Medical Association has submitted a corresponding position paper (Bundesärztekammer, 2023; Bundesrat, 2023). The 2025 coalition agreement announced an "iMVZ regulation act".

The structural diagnosis is therefore not that investor-led MVZ close public-provision gaps across the territory. They concentrate on high-return specialist segments in care-rich areas, while the gaps in securing care in structurally weak areas remain unaddressed, and the public sector's public-provision responsibility — that of the Länder and municipalities — is not substituted by private capital.

This conflation has arisen not through ill intent but through fiscal inertia and an unclear architecture of responsibility:

Where responsibility is not clearly allocated, whoever is within reach takes it on.

In the German system this is regularly the contribution-financed social insurance — visible in the hospital cross-financing through DRG revenues (Deutsche Krankenhausgesellschaft, 2025), in the non-contribution-covered benefits in statutory pension insurance of around 63 to 112 billion euros depending on the demarcation (Bundesrechnungshof, 2023; Deutsche Rentenversicherung, 2024), in the *Bürgergeld*–GKV flat rate with an annual shortfall of around 9 billion euros (IGES Institut, 2024), and in the de facto assumption of advice and care tasks by office-based doctors and hospitals that, by their insurance mandate, would properly fall to municipal or Länder structures.

The pattern is everywhere the same: public provision shrinks to the statutory minimum, assistance reaches the fiscal limits of municipal budgets — and insurance absorbs the structural gap from the contribution pool of the insured, without this being openly identified as a paradigm shift in social policy.

3.4 Market — Individual, Premium-Based

Definition and Constitutive Features

The market logic organises equivalence-based, private-law risk cover in competition. Its constitutive features are: first, the individual contractual relationship between policyholder and insurance undertaking; second, premium calculation on the basis of individual risk characteristics; third, the

competitive orientation of several providers in a regulated market; fourth, the supervisory framework set by the Federal Financial Supervisory Authority (BaFin) and its supervisory duties under the Insurance Supervision Act.

The market in the welfare-state context is not the unsteered market of economic theory but a highly regulated special market with considerable constitutional bindings — in particular as regards lifelong calculation (ageing provisions), the obligation to contract in the basic tariff, and tariff supervision. The market logic is sensible and valuable where individual risk heterogeneity and individual diversity of preference argue for appropriate differentiation — and where, at the same time, basic social protection is secured by other means.

Historical Development in Germany

German private health insurance developed in parallel with statutory health insurance, as insurance for those population groups that were exempt from GKV compulsory insurance: at first civil servants (via the public-servant assistance scheme), the self-employed, members of the liberal professions and employees above the annual earnings threshold (Wasem, 1996). This split between the GKV and the PKV is a German peculiarity that exists in no other large European welfare state in comparable form. It has historical reasons and political forces of inertia that arise from the property guarantee of acquired entitlements (BVerfG, 2009).

Important for understanding the market logic is that, in the German health-care system, it is present not only via the PKV but also in two further areas: first, as private supplementary long-term care insurance alongside social long-term care insurance; second, as an element within the GKV itself (supplementary insurance, optional tariffs, deductible models). These internal market elements were introduced by the GKV modernisation acts of the 2000s and have already, in part, hybridised the insurance logic of the GKV.

Current Manifestations

The central manifestations of the market logic in health care are: full insurance in the PKV, with around 8.79 million insured persons (as of 2025) — though around 53 per cent of these, almost 4.6 million people, are civil servants, judges and their assistance-eligible family members (Gesamtverband der Deutschen Versicherungswirtschaft, 2023; PKV-Verband, 2026); the supplementary assistance tariffs for civil servants; private supplementary long-term care insurance; the hospital optional tariffs and senior-physician optional tariffs of the GKV; supplementary insurance for dental treatment, spectacles, alternative practitioners and foreign travel (around 31.98 million contracts in 2025); and various add-on insurances in health-insurance distribution. The structure of the figures is analytically instructive: more than half of the German PKV full-insurance portfolio is in effect a special form of state-subsidised insurance — the public-servant assistance scheme is financed from the budgets of the federal government, the Länder and the municipalities, and the supplementary PKV residual-cost insurance is for the assistance-eligible practically without alternative (94 per cent of civil servants are privately insured; PKV-Verband, 2025). The “free” market logic of the PKV thereby in effect reaches only some 4 million people beyond the civil-servant portfolio.

Structural Properties

In its pure form the market logic is efficient in differentiating the supply of services and in adapting to individual preferences. It is structurally weak in social risk-sharing — it cannot take on high risks without either pushing premiums beyond bounds or engaging in selection in favour of good risks. It is weakly mandated democratically — insurance contracts are concluded under private law, not negotiated politically. It is only of limited functional capacity in competitive terms, because the costs of switching in health insurance and pension provision are extremely high on account of the ageing provisions.

An important structural observation: the German PKV construction has long generated a systematic risk selection — young, healthy, high-income insured persons are burdened by the GKV contribution assessment and removed from the solidarity equalisation of the GKV through the possibility of entering the PKV. This selection works to the disadvantage of the GKV and has long been documented in the health-economics literature (Wasem, 1996; Max-Planck-Institut für Sozialrecht und Sozialpolitik, 2007). Its correction is highly contested politically and has for decades failed on considerations of grandfathering — which underlines the structural character of the PKV–GKV conflation as an architectural problem.

Typical Pathologies of Conflation

The typical pathology of the market logic in the German health-care system is its unresolved interface with the insurance logic of the GKV. Here two structural breaks are found: first, the division of the insured portfolio between the GKV and the PKV by criteria of income and occupational estate, which follows neither a clear social-policy justification nor generates a coherent competitive structure; second, the partial internalisation of market elements into the GKV (supplementary insurance, optional tariffs), which erodes the solidarity of the GKV risk community without opening up genuine freedom of choice to the insured.

An architectural clarification at the PKV–GKV interface would not abolish the market logic but situate it at a clear structural point — as supplementary insurance above a uniform basic cover, comparable to the Dutch construction. This question is elaborated in detail in Chapter 4 as the third case.

3.5 The Matrix in Overall View, and Pathologies of Conflation

The four logics unfolded in the preceding sections yield, in their ideal-typical pure form, four clearly demarcable fields. Empirically, however, the German welfare state is marked by a multitude of conflations that are not randomly distributed but form patterns. Table 2 systematises the most important types of conflation.

Type of conflation	Pathology	Application (Ch. 4)
Insurance × Social Assistance	Social-assistance tasks are financed through insurance contributions, although neither contribution assessment nor the logic of entitlement is designed for them	4.1 — <i>Bürgergeld</i> and the GKV: systematic under-funding of the flat-rate contribution
Insurance × Public Provision	Infrastructure costs of territorial public provision are shifted into insurance financing, without the insurer controlling the investment decision	4.2 — Hospital capacity funding: dual financing as conflation
Insurance × Market	Market selection mechanisms feed back into solidarity-based insurance, without any coherent interface architecture in place	4.3 — The PKV–GKV interface: risk selection and the erosion of solidarity
All four at the institutional level	At the level of a single care institution all four logics converge, without their architectural allocation being clarified	4.4 — The primary-care centre: all four logics in a single node of care

Table 2: *Types of conflation between the four logics (author’s own illustration)*

Table 2 shows the pattern that produces German reform exhaustion: the conflations are not random — they follow a recurring structure. In every case a task that would ideal-typically be at home in one logic is shifted into another logic, without the latter’s constitutive features being designed for it. The receiving logic is thereby structurally overstrained, because it brings to the extraneous task neither the fiscal resources nor the steering mechanisms nor the democratic mandate. The ceding logic is at the same time hollowed out, because it gives up its constitutive task and replaces it with an inconsistent hybrid construction.

This pattern can be traced exemplarily in the four cases of the following chapter. It is the central thesis of this paper that an architectural clarification must begin precisely at these points of conflation — not through a big-bang reform but through successive disentanglement, beginning with the most costly and most visible logic breaks. The transition path needed for this, and a concrete governance proposal, are elaborated in Chapter 5.

4 Four Application Cases

The matrix developed in Chapter 3 is applied in what follows to four exemplary cases. The order is chosen didactically: it begins with the clearest type of conflation (*Bürgergeld*–GKV) and works through the currently prominent hospital reform and the structurally deep-seated PKV–GKV interface to the primary-care centre, in which all four logics converge at the level of a single institution. Each case follows a uniform sub-structure: diagnosis of the logic break, reconstruction of previous reform attempts, a sketch of an architectural clarification, and a discussion of the expected effects.

4.1 Bürgergeld–GKV — The Insurance–Social Assistance Conflation

Diagnosis of the Logic Break

Recipients of *Bürgergeld* under Social Code Book II are compulsorily insured in the statutory health insurance system. Their contributions are assumed by the federal government through a flat-rate contribution, the level of which is governed by § 251 of Social Code Book V. This construction is the result of a historically grown pragmatism: when Hartz IV merged the former unemployment assistance and the social assistance for employable persons in 2005, the compulsory insurance was carried over from the earlier unemployment assistance — and with it the construction whereby the federal government pays a flat rate to the sickness funds.

From the perspective of the Welfare State Matrix this is a classic Insurance–Social Assistance conflation: the benefit recipients are not in employment — by definition, therefore, they cannot make an income-proportional contribution to the risk community. Their cover is accordingly a social-assistance task of the political community. Yet it is not financed from the federal budget but from the contribution pool of the GKV — mediated by a flat rate whose level the federal government sets unilaterally and which has for more than a decade fallen systematically short of the actual costs of care.

In its reports of 2016 and 2022, commissioned by the Federal Ministry of Health, the IGES Institute quantified the structural under-funding: by the concurring assessment of the GKV-Spitzenverband and several individual funds, the flat-rate contribution covers less than half of the actual costs of care. The difference is cross-subsidised from the contribution income of insured persons in employment (GKV-Spitzenverband, 2025; BKK Dachverband, 2026; Techniker Krankenkasse, 2026). The Bundesrat formally criticised this in its resolution of 30 January 2026 and called on the federal government to set the flat-rate contribution at a cost-covering level (Bundesrat, 2026).

On 11 September 2025 the administrative board of the GKV-Spitzenverband resolved — without precedent in the history of statutory self-government — to bring an action against the Federal Republic of Germany; the Higher Social Court of North Rhine-Westphalia has jurisdiction at first instance. The structural message of this resolution to litigate is clear: the existing construction cannot be repaired by a mere increase in the flat rate but is, in its basic structure, legally assailable. This is precisely the point at which the architectural diagnosis begins.

Figure 2: Bürgergeld and the GKV — a social assistance benefit financed through an insurance system (author’s own illustration)

Previous Reform Attempts

Previous reform attempts at this point have concentrated on the level and modalities of the flat rate. The flat rate has been raised several times, most recently with the Statutory Health Insurance Financial Stabilisation Act of 2022. Calculation formulas have been modified, indexations introduced and suspended again. What did not take place was a structural discussion of the logic assignment itself. The question was always: how high must the flat rate be in order to cover costs? — never: does this task belong to the insurance logic or to the social-assistance logic?

This narrowing is not accidental. It follows from the political incentive structure: shifting the health-insurance financing of *Bürgergeld* recipients into the federal budget would make some 9 to 11 billion euros of additional expenditure visible there — funds that today disappear into the opaque cross-subsidisation mechanism of GKV contribution financing.

The current construction is thus politically and economically attractive for the federal government — and economically painful for the contributors, who do not recognise it, because the logic break remains hidden within the contribution structure.

Sketch of an Architectural Clarification

The architecturally consistent solution is to transfer the health-insurance financing for *Bürgergeld* recipients out of the insurance logic into the social-assistance logic. Concretely this would mean: the health-insurance benefits for *Bürgergeld* recipients continue to be provided by the sickness funds — but they are no longer financed from contribution income, but from a direct federal subsidy at the level of the actual costs of care. This would correspond to the logic of a contracting model: the federal government does not pay a flat-rate contribution but reimburses the funds for the costs of care actually incurred per *Bürgergeld*-insured person, on an empirical basis.

This construction has three structural consequences.

First, the fiscal burden would become visible — it would appear in the federal budget as an item of expenditure and no longer in the opaque contribution pool of the GKV. That is politically uncomfortable but architecturally consistent: social assistance is a task of the political community and must be accounted for in the federal budget.

Second, the cross-subsidisation from the contribution income of insured persons in employment would end — which would directly relieve the general contribution rate. For the first time in decades, the GKV contribution debate would once again reflect the actual insurance relationship, not the shadow financing of an extraneous logic.

Third, the sickness funds would retain their operational role — they would remain providers of care but would no longer be misused as shadow financiers of a social-assistance task.

Expected Effects

The first fiscal effect would be a shift of some 9 to 11 billion euros in annual volume out of the GKV contribution pool into the federal budget. This would not be additional expenditure by the political community — it would be a making-visible of expenditure that already exists. Politically it is likely to generate considerable tension, because the fiscal visibility of *Bürgergeld* health insurance would reach an order of magnitude that is attractive for budget-policy lines of conflict. But that is precisely the democratically desirable result: a benefit of the political community must be democratically negotiable. The current construction withdraws this negotiation from the political public by relocating it into the opaque contribution structure.

Structurally, the clarification would at the same time resolve a preliminary question for further architectural clarifications: once the social-assistance tasks are removed from the GKV, the GKV contribution debate can focus on the actual insurance relationship — and thus, for the first time again, make reliable statements about which contribution rate is actually required for which insurance benefits. This is the structural precondition of any serious contribution-assessment reform.

4.2 Hospital Capacity Funding — The Insurance–Public Provision Conflation

Diagnosis of the Logic Break

Since the Hospital Financing Act of 1972, German hospital financing has rested on so-called dual financing: the Länder are responsible for investment costs, the sickness funds for operating costs. This dual structure was conceived as a clean architectural clarification. It assigned the territorial care structure (public provision) to the Länder and the treatment costs of the individual patient (insurance) to the sickness funds.

In practical implementation this separation has eroded for decades in favour of the insurance logic. The Länder systematically fail to meet their investment responsibility: the Hospital Rating Report of RWI Essen and the annual survey of hospital planning and investment financing in the Länder produced by the German Hospital Federation document a progressive investment gap. In 2024 the investment ratio of the Länder, relative to the adjusted hospital costs, stood at only 2.8 per cent — against 9.7 per cent in 1991 and an economy-wide investment ratio of 21.85 per cent (Deutsche Krankenhausgesellschaft, 2025). The investment backlog accumulated over three decades is put at more than 50 billion euros in the relevant literature and trade-union analysis (ver.di, 2009; Augurzky et al., 2025). The missing investment funds are in effect compensated from the operating funds of the sickness funds: the DRG revenues are used to a considerable extent for the preservation of fabric, because the investment financing of the Länder is insufficient (BVMed, 2019; Augurzky et al., 2025). The territorial public provision is thus in effect co-financed by the insurance logic — without the insurance side controlling the investment decisions.

The result is a double steering gap. The Länder make investment decisions without bearing the fiscal consequences of their own investment under-funding. The sickness funds bear a considerable part of the fiscal consequences without being able to make the investment decisions. In no other major infrastructure logic of the German state would such a decoupling of decision and financing responsibility be politically acceptable. In health care it has become permanent routine.

Previous Reform Attempts

Hospital financing is one of the most reform-active fields of the German welfare state. Among the more recent major reform waves are the Hospital Structure Act of 2015, the Nursing Staff Strengthening Act of 2018, the nursing-staff lower-limit ordinances, the MDK Reform Act of 2019, the Hospital Future Act of 2020 and, most recently, the Hospital Care Improvement Act (KHVVG) of 2024. Each of these reforms has achieved selective improvements — they have not resolved the structural conflation between the insurance and public-provision logics.

With the introduction of capacity-funding flat rates, the KHVVG took a step in the right direction: in the DRG system it separates out a share of the remuneration explicitly as capacity remuneration and decouples it from case numbers. This capacity component is in effect a public-provision financing, because it remunerates the structural fact of a hospital's being available — irrespective of whether treatment cases are actually billed.

What remains architecturally problematic, however, is that this capacity component continues to be financed from GKV contributions, not from the tax revenues of the Länder. The logic conflation is thus carried forward at a higher level — it is made cosmetically more visible, but not resolved.

Sketch of an Architectural Clarification

The architecturally consistent solution separates the public-provision component completely from the insurance component. Concretely this would mean: the capacity funding — the structural securing of the existence of hospitals in a defined care area — is financed entirely from tax revenues. The federal government and the Länder bear this responsibility jointly, with a clear assignment: the Länder are responsible for regional care planning and ensure the capacity structures in accordance with the planning framework. The federal government supports the Länder in this task — analogous to the federal–Länder pact for universities or infrastructures — through earmarked financial resources.

The sickness funds continue to finance the treatment component — the individual insurance cases that a patient triggers in a hospital. This treatment remuneration follows the insurance logic: per case, per service, within the patient’s acquired insurance entitlement. The DRG remuneration is reduced to this treatment component and is structurally decoupled from the capacity question.

This clarification produces a series of constitutive changes:

First, investment decisions and capacity funding are once again brought together in one hand — the Länder decide and bear the fiscal consequences.

Second, the sickness funds become pure insurance carriers again: they pay for actual services to the insured, not for the structures of an extraneous logic.

Third, the hospital planning of the Länder once again becomes politically binding, because it can no longer be compensated by the DRG revenues of the hospitals.

This architectural clarification stands in fundamental opposition to the occasionally discussed model of a monistic hospital financing in the hands of the GKV, which envisages a merger of operating and investment financing within the sickness funds. From the perspective of the Welfare State Matrix, such a monistic model would not resolve the conflation between insurance and public provision but deepen it structurally: the public-provision component would be permanently relocated into the contribution pools, and the Länder would be definitively released from their territorial responsibility. Fiscally, too, the conversion would be problematic — under a monistic model, according to calculations by the joint self-government, the flat-rate funding, the residual hospital-financing claims and the investment backlog, each amounting to several billion euros, would have to be fully passed on to the funding bodies, which would raise contribution rates accordingly (Rürup, 2008; DKG, 2025). What is architecturally consistent is not the fusion of the logics but their clean separation — investment as public provision with the Länder, treatment as an insurance service with the sickness funds.

Expected Effects

The first fiscal effect would be a shift of investment and capacity costs out of the GKV contribution pool into the Länder budgets — financed via a federal–Länder agreement. The order of magnitude can be approximately determined from the available data: the annual fabric-preserving investment requirement, by the calculation of the joint self-government, is around 7 billion euros (DKG, 2025); to this is added the dissolution of the cumulative investment backlog of more than 50 billion euros over a medium-term horizon (ver.di, 2009; Augurzky et al., 2025); the capacity flat rate introduced in the KHVVG moreover corresponds to a volume in the single-digit billions, which would architecturally likewise have to be shifted to the Länder. Overall, a fiscal redistribution in the double-digit billions per

year is to be expected. This shift would not, however, be additional expenditure — it would be a relocation of something that already takes place today, only at the wrong architectural place.

Structurally, the clarification would produce several follow-on effects that would make themselves felt positively in political terms. The hospital planning of the Länder would once again become what it should be — a politically accountable structural decision about regional care density. The DRG debate would free itself of the incentive distortions that are notorious today (driving up case numbers to preserve fabric). And the hospital landscape would consolidate along the politically intended care planning, not along the chance revenue position of individual hospitals. This consolidation may indeed lead to the closure of hospital sites — but it would then be the result of a democratically accountable structural decision, not the outcome of a creeping erosion through DRG incentives.

4.3 The PKV–GKV Interface — The Market–Insurance Conflation

Diagnosis of the Logic Break

The separation between statutory and private health insurance is the most German of all German welfare-state peculiarities. It has its roots in the Bismarckian construction principle — social insurance was conceived for the dependently employed workforce, not for the self-employed or the occupational estates in public service. From this historical origin an institutional architecture has developed that today places two separate insurance systems side by side: the solidarity-based GKV for the compulsorily insured and the market-organised PKV for those exempt from insurance.

In the Welfare State Matrix this is a classic Market–Insurance conflation: two logics — solidarity-based insurance and market-based risk cover — are not connected to one another through clearly defined interfaces but separated from one another by a rigid portfolio boundary along criteria of income and occupational estate.

The consequence is a systematic risk selection: young, healthy, high-income insured persons can switch to the PKV and are removed from the solidarity equalisation of the GKV. This selection has long been documented in the health-economics literature (Wasem, 1996; Max-Planck-Institut für Sozialrecht und Sozialpolitik, 2007) — it is not the accidental by-product of a good construction but a systemic consequence of the architecture.

In its judgment on the PKV basic tariff of 10 June 2009, the Federal Constitutional Court confirmed the fundamental constitutional conformity of the dual health-insurance structure, but at the same time required an obligation to contract in the basic tariff and recognised the social function of the PKV (BVerfG, 2009). It thereby entrenched the structural hybridity of the PKV — as a market instrument with inscribed social functions — in constitutional law, without resolving the underlying architectural conflation.

Previous Reform Attempts

For two decades the PKV–GKV interface has been the arena of a citizens’-insurance debate that regularly founders on the logic conflation. The concept of a citizens’ insurance (*Bürgerversicherung*) was developed in 2003 in the Commission for Sustainability in the Financing of the Social Security Systems (the Rürup Commission) set up by the SPD–Green federal government, decisively shaped by the later Federal Health Minister Karl Lauterbach (Bundesministerium für Gesundheit und Soziale

Sicherung, 2003; Lauterbach, 2004). It envisaged a uniform insurance for all residents, with income-related contributions including all types of income, and a uniform benefits catalogue. Against this, the CDU/CSU and the FDP, and later in part the German Council of Economic Experts, propagated the model of a health premium (also: per-capita flat rate): income-independent flat-rate contributions with a tax-financed social equalisation (Sachverständigenrat zur Begutachtung der gesamtwirtschaftlichen Entwicklung, 2004; Rürup, 2003). In the Statutory Health Insurance Competition Strengthening Act of 2007, under the Grand Coalition, the two camps found no architectural compromise but agreed on the Health Fund — a construction that could be developed further in either direction without committing to one (Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung, 2012). In the subsequent legislative terms, too — the citizens'-insurance motion of the SPD parliamentary group in 2017, the coalition negotiations of 2017/18, the traffic-light coalition negotiations of 2021 — neither of the two architectural paths was taken. In practice, both models have failed to bring about a structural clarification, because both had to respect the grandfathered status of PKV-insured persons and were thus from the outset realisable only in a watered-down variant.

The structural observation here: a citizens'-insurance reform that would transfer today's PKV full insurance into a universal GKV does not founder on a lack of political will, but on the constitutional property guarantee of the acquired entitlement rights. The reform would be realisable only over a transition period of several decades — which makes it politically unattractive. It is precisely for this reason that the logic conflation is so persistent at this point: it cannot be resolved simply by a political majority decision but requires an architecturally considered transition construction.

Sketch of an Architectural Clarification

The architecturally consistent solution is not the abolition of the market logic in the health-insurance system but its repositioning at a clear structural place. The Dutch Zorgverzekeringswet model, implemented since 2006, offers an international reference whose architecture can be transferred to the German context — though not in every operational detail.

The Dutch model establishes a uniform compulsory health insurance for all residents, whose benefits catalogue is defined by law and whose implementation takes place through privately organised health insurers in regulated competition (Schäfer et al., 2010; Kroneman et al., 2016; Wammes et al., 2024). The insurers compete for insured persons through the level of contributions and contract structures, but are obliged to accept applicants and are subject to a strict risk-structure equalisation. The insured person pays an income-related component to the state (which flows into a central risk-equalisation fund) and a nominal, uniform insurer premium to their chosen provider. Supplementary insurance above the uniform benefits catalogue is organised privately, through the market.

Transferred to the German context, this architecture would establish a uniform basic insurance for all residents — with income-related contribution financing along today's GKV logic. Today's PKV full insurance would be transferred step by step into this basic insurance in a transition model — preserving the acquired entitlement rights and the ageing provisions. The market logic would be retained, but at a clear structural place: as supplementary insurance above the uniform basic insurance, with genuine competition in a defined market. Such supplementary-insurance markets are well established internationally: in the Dutch model around 84 per cent of the population hold voluntary supplementary policies — typically for dental prostheses, alternative therapies,

physiotherapy beyond the basic level, or private rooms in hospital (Wammes et al., 2024); functioning supplementary-insurance segments also exist in Switzerland, in France (*assurance complémentaire santé*) and in the United Kingdom, coexisting with the respective basic provision without competing with it in the architecture.

Expected Effects

The first structural effect would be the dissolution of today's risk selection. The solidarity equalisation would encompass all residents — young and old, healthy and sick, high-income and low-income. The current contribution burden of GKV-insured persons would change accordingly: tending to the disadvantage of today's PKV-insured persons (who retain their entitlements but would additionally participate in the solidarity community) and to the advantage of today's GKV-insured persons (whose contribution base would broaden).

This shift would be politically highly sensitive, because it touches directly on the expectation security of today's PKV-insured persons. It is precisely for this reason that the transition architecture is decisive: today's PKV full insurance must be transferred into the uniform basic insurance step by step in a generational perspective — over some two to three decades — with a clear crediting of the ageing provisions and without abrupt income losses for the insured. A German parallel shows that such cross-generational architectural conversions are indeed realisable: the conversion to the deferred taxation of retirement income, decided with the Retirement Income Act of 5 July 2004, followed the requirements of the Federal Constitutional Court of 6 March 2002 and is designed for a transition phase from 2005 until probably 2058 — that is, over more than five decades. It is precisely here that the character of architectural clarification as a generational task becomes apparent: it is not realisable within one legislative term, but it is realisable — if the willingness exists to embark on a long-term path.

4.4 The Primary-Care Centre — All Four Logics at the Institutional Level

Diagnosis of Conflation at the Institutional Level

The primary-care centre (*Primärversorgungszentrum, PVZ*) is the institutional answer to a twofold problem: the erosion of general-practitioner care across the territory, and the inadequate integration between the outpatient, social-psychiatric and municipal care structures. The Advisory Council recommended the establishment of primary-care centres as a central reform element in its reports of 2018 and 2023 (Sachverständigenrat, 2018, 2023); in a position paper in 2025, the Diakonie presented concrete models for their implementation (Diakonie, 2025); Schröter (2024) diagnosed the reform need of German primary medicine in an influential review.

From the perspective of the Welfare State Matrix, the primary-care centre is a particularly instructive case, because here all four logics converge at the level of a single care institution. The medical and non-medical care is an insurance service — it is billed through the GKV. The local capacity structure — the plain existence of an institution in a defined care area — is public provision. The social support, the link to addiction services, the social work with the patient is social assistance. The free choice of institution by the insured and the competition of several providers is a market element.

Today's German care landscape has no institutional place at which these four logics would be architecturally clearly assigned. General-practitioner practices are organised primarily along insurance logic, with municipal and social functions that regularly depend on the engagement of individuals, not on a structural assignment. MVZ structures compensate for care gaps on a return-oriented, investor-borne basis — which structurally strengthens the market logic but tends to weaken the public-provision function. A municipal sponsorship that would take on the local capacity structure as a public-provision task exists in Germany only in exceptional cases.

Previous Reform Attempts

The German discussion about primary-care centres has currently entered a phase of heightened political attention. Both the coalition agreement of the current federal government and the KBV positioning of 2026 take up the theme; several Länder have set up pilot projects. The HÄPPI model ('Hausärztliches Primärversorgungszentrum — Patientenversorgung Interprofessionell') developed by the German Association of General Practitioners was initially piloted in Baden-Württemberg; since May 2025 Bavaria has been funding a comparable model project at seven general-practitioner practices with around 650,000 euros over three years, and Rhineland-Palatinate has prepared its own pilot for July 2025 (Deutscher Hausärzteverband, 2025). The structural weakness of these initiatives, however, is that they do not pose the architectural question: which component of a primary-care centre belongs in which logic? Who bears the fiscal and political responsibility for which function?

An international comparison makes this clear. Since 2015 Austria has systematically built up primary-care units (*Primärversorgungseinheiten*, PVE). The first model started in 2015 in Vienna, within a conceptual framework that was at the time co-shaped under the director-general's office of the Vienna Hospital Association (see Appendix B); the actual expansion push came in 2022, when Austria mobilised around 100 million euros for primary care from the EU Recovery and Resilience Plan. In July 2025 the hundredth PVE was opened — including 13 units specifically oriented towards paediatric and adolescent medicine. The Austrian model is distinguished precisely by the fact that it separates the spheres of responsibility clearly in architectural terms: the medical service runs as an insurance service through the Austrian Health Insurance Fund, the infrastructural establishment is funded from EU and federal resources, and the regional anchoring takes place via the Land and the social-insurance carrier.

Sketch of an Architectural Clarification

The architecturally consistent construction of a primary-care centre in Germany would assign the four logics at the institutional level as follows.

The insurance component — the medical and non-medical treatment of the individual patient — is financed by the sickness funds, within a suitable remuneration model (a mixed model of flat rates, selective contracts and quality components).

The public-provision component — the local capacity structure, the spatial and personnel infrastructure of the institution — is financed jointly by the federal government, the Land and the municipality, within a regional care plan.

The social-assistance component — the social support, the social work with the patient, the social prescribing — is financed through the municipal social budgets and, where appropriate, federal programmes. Social prescribing here refers to the care approach originating in the British National

Health Service, in which primary-care professionals involve so-called link workers who connect patients with non-medically grounded complaints — loneliness, social isolation, financial hardship, lack of access to exercise or educational opportunities — to corresponding municipal and civil-society support structures; an EU-funded research project led by the Charité Berlin is currently testing this approach in several German Länder (Charité — Universitätsmedizin Berlin, 2024; Heintze et al., 2023).

The market component — the free choice of institution by the insured and the quality competition between different providers — is structurally permitted, without undermining the care obligation of public provision.

The question of who, in the primary-care centre thus understood, coordinates the integrative care of the individual patient is architecturally central and must be explicitly clarified. A two-tier coordination model is proposed:

At the patient level, a firmly assigned navigator function — for instance a community health nurse or a specially qualified link worker — takes on the task of continuous support across the four functional areas, so that a stable point of contact is available to the patient or person in need of help.

At the institutional level, a multi-professional management structure (typically medical management, nursing management and municipal social-service management jointly) brings together the operational steering of the four logics, without any single logic absorbing the others. This management function can in principle also be delegated to a management company specialised for the purpose — provided it remains ensured that the steering stays multi-professionally anchored and oriented to the four logics, and is not subordinated to a single business-management logic. This ensures that ‘coordinated alongside one another’ does not mean ‘past one another’ but an institutionalised, named and accountable, quality-assured integrative care.

This clarification makes it possible to conceive the primary-care centre as the institutional node of the local care architecture — with clearly assigned spheres of responsibility, rather than as a hybrid point of steering dispute between the federal government, the Länder, the municipalities and the self-government. It is this architectural clarification that will decisively shape the probability of success of the German primary-care reform.

Where responsibility is clearly assigned, viable structures emerge. Where responsibility remains unclear, structures emerge that are stabilisable neither fiscally nor operationally.

Expected Effects

The first structural effect would be the establishment of a new institutional place at which the four logics do not conflate but interact in a coordinated way. That is the decisive conceptual difference from the hybrid structures existing today: in the architecturally clarified primary-care centre there is not one logic that absorbs all the others (as the insurance logic regularly does today), but four logics that act alongside one another in a clearly assigned distribution of tasks — steered by the two-tier coordination model sketched above at the patient and institutional levels.

The fiscal follow-on effects are less dramatic than in the three preceding cases, because primary care is comparatively small within the overall architecture of the welfare state. The structural significance is, however, considerable: the primary-care centre is the institutional interface at which the welfare

state reaches the individual citizen in everyday care. If this interface is architecturally clearly designed, this benefits not only primary care but the entire care architecture — because at a decisive point it establishes a model of logic clarification that can be transferred to other levels of care.

The primary-care centre can thus become the exemplary learning field of architectural clarification — small in scale, high in instruction.

5 Transition Path and Governance

The preceding chapters have developed the Welfare State Matrix as a diagnostic model and related it to four application cases. But diagnosis is not therapy. By ‘transition path’, what is meant in the following is the way that leads from today’s structure, marked by logic conflation, to an architecturally clarified welfare-state structure — a way that connects the structural import of the diagnosis with politically realistic steps organised in stages. This chapter sketches such a transition path. It is deliberately not a reform blueprint but a structural sketch: four building blocks that, taken together, can yield a generational path of architectural clarification.

5.1 Institutional Disentanglement as a Concept

Before a concrete governance proposal can be formulated, the theoretical form of the transition meant here must be clarified. Over the past three decades, institutionalist welfare-state research has shown that developed welfare states change their shape not through fundamental upheavals but through accumulated incremental shifts. In his work on the logic of ‘increasing returns’, Pierson (2000) described why social-policy structures are path-dependent and why their reformability possesses a specific topology. Streeck and Thelen (2005) proposed the five modes of institutional change — displacement, layering, drift, conversion and exhaustion — as an analytical vocabulary with which the typical mode of German welfare-state development can be reconstructed precisely as ‘layering’ with persistent ‘drift’ effects. Hacker (2004) captured the same finding under the term of the hidden politics of welfare-state retrenchment.

What this research shows in a way that is decisive for the argument pursued here is this: the specific form of institutional change in developed welfare states is not reform-as-a-whole but the successive modification of individual structural components while the historically grown overall configuration continues to take effect. This is not a political weakness but an institutional peculiarity of corporatist welfare states. An architectural clarification must respect this peculiarity — it cannot be conceived as a big bang without endangering the functional capacity of the very structures whose clarification it pursues.

The transition path proposed in this paper can therefore be understood as institutional disentanglement: a process, stretched over time and organised in stages, in which the functional areas that overlap today are gradually separated to the point where every component is unambiguously assigned to one logic. Put figuratively: four sets that, in their present configuration, form several zones of overlap are reorganised so that the overlaps dissolve and defined interfaces emerge in their place. The topology changes not through the abolition of the components but through the clarification of their points of contact.

Three properties characterise this disentanglement process.

First, it is sequential: not all logic breaks are addressed simultaneously, but in an order oriented to the fiscal volume, the political negotiability and the follow-on effect of each individual clarification step.

Second, it is asymmetric: not all four logics are affected to the same degree. The greatest needs for clarification lie at the interface between the insurance and social-assistance logics (*Bürgergeld*–GKV) and between the insurance and public-provision logics (hospital capacity).

Third, it is cross-generational: it claims the political time horizon in which the Stability and Growth Act of 1967 or the debt-brake reform of 2009 were also prepared, decided and institutionally anchored.

An architectural clarification of this order of magnitude is not a project of one legislative term.

From this concept it follows at the same time what institutional disentanglement is not. It is not a dismantling of the welfare state. It is not a privatisation programme. It is not the dissolution of solidarity-based insurance in favour of a pure market logic, or the shifting of insurance services into state social assistance. On the contrary, it is the precondition for each of these four logics to remain viable within its own functional area. Conflation does not destroy one logic in favour of another; it hollows out several logics at once. Clarification protects each one of them.

At this point an obvious objection is to be addressed. It runs: whoever places architectural clarity and transparency at the beginning thereby places structure above harmony — and turns away from an integrative, patient- and client-oriented care, in which precisely the transitions between the spheres would have to be designed as fluid. This objection mistakes the direction of the argument. Architectural clarification is not the opposite of integrative care but its condition. Integrative care oriented to the patient or person in need of help requires that the actors involved know their respective responsibility, that their interfaces are defined, and that at every point of handover a named body takes on responsibility. Conflated logics produce not integration but diffuse responsibility — and it is precisely this diffusion through which the patient today falls between the responsibilities. The two-tier coordination model sketched for the primary-care centre in Chapter 4.4 — a navigator function at the patient level, multi-professional management at the institutional level — is the operational answer to this objection: it shows that architectural clarification and lived care integration do not exclude one another but condition one another. Clarity does not come instead of integration, but so that integration can reliably succeed at all.

Figure 3 visualises the target architecture towards which the disentanglement path is directed: four logics clarified in their constitutive features, each with a structural principle peculiar to it and a consequence following from it for the institutional design. The figure is intended as a test standard — as a target image against which every individual reform decision of the coming years can be examined for its architectural consistency.

It is thus not a reform programme but its frame of orientation.

Figure 3: Four Principles — the target architecture of a coherent welfare-state structure (author's own illustration)

5.2 A Welfare State Architecture Act

Why is a separate act needed at all — and not merely a succession of careful individual reforms? The answer follows directly from the diagnosis. Individual reforms regularly operate within the existing, already conflated logic structure; they can relieve individual symptoms but typically reproduce the conflation or generate a new one elsewhere — the layering mechanism described in Chapter 5.1 with Streeck and Thelen (2005). An architectural clarification therefore requires an overarching regulatory self-binding of the legislator: a rule that does not design individual social benefits but defines the framework against which every future individual design must be measured. Without such a framework, architectural clarification is left to the chance of changing majorities and departmental interests — and thus structurally improbable.

The concrete governance proposal of this paper is therefore to anchor the architectural clarification in a Welfare State Architecture Act. Such an act would not reform individual social benefits but set the regulatory framework within which social benefits are organised. For this type of act — a federal

framework that defines a system of objectives rather than individual measures — there are established precedents in German legislative history. The Stability and Growth Act of 1967, with the magic quadrilateral of macroeconomic objectives, created a binding system of objectives and a framework for stability-oriented action at all levels of the state (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie, 2015); the debt brake introduced into the Basic Law in 2009 set a regulatory debt rule as a framework. Both examples are, however, not to be understood as uncontested success stories — on the contrary: the substantive performance of both sets of rules is contested, and the debt brake itself was fundamentally reformed in March 2025 after intensive debate (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025). It is precisely this finding that is instructive for the proposal advanced here: a regulatory framework act must be conceived as open to revision. It serves as a type-model for the form — a framework instead of an individual measure — not as a guarantee of a particular outcome. A Welfare State Architecture Act would consequently have to be equipped from the outset with a regulated review and adjustment mechanism.

Four elements would have to be laid down in such an act.

First, the definitional separation of the four logics — a definition, anchored in the text of the act, of what Insurance, Social Assistance, Public Provision and Market each mean in the welfare-state context, and which constitutive features distinguish their pure form.

Second, the financing assignment per logic: the insurance logic is financed through contributions, the social-assistance logic from the federal budget, public provision from the taxes of the federal government, the Länder and the municipalities, the market logic from premiums.

Third, the responsibility assignment: the federal government is responsible for the regulatory framework and the federally uniformly defined social-assistance benefits, the Länder for the territorial public provision, the municipalities for the local social-assistance and public-provision structures, the self-government for the insurance carriers.

Fourth, a conflict-resolution mechanism for hybrid benefits — that is, a clearly regulated procedure for how, at the interfaces between the logics, responsibility is assigned and financial burdens are distributed.

Such an architecture act would be constitutionally demanding. It would touch on property guarantees (in particular in the area of PKV entitlements), municipal self-government rights (in the area of public provision) and the welfare-state principle (Articles 20 and 28 of the Basic Law). But it would be constitutionally possible — as the debt-brake reform of 2009 or the federalism reforms of 2003 and 2006 have shown. Architectural clarification is a regulatory self-binding task of a similar order of magnitude to these reforms, and it can take the same constitutional path.

5.3 A Parallel Restructuring of the Social Code

The Social Code in its present form is a legacy of the early 1970s — the SGB architecture that is based on the line of the welfare-state tradition of the Federal Republic and divides the individual fields of social benefits into numbered books (I to XIV). This architecture is more than fifty years old and is organised not along the four logics but along the historical sequence in which the fields of social

benefits arose. In the systematics of the law, it reproduces precisely those conflations that the Welfare State Matrix diagnoses.

A consistent architectural clarification would therefore require a parallel restructuring of the Social Code along the four logics. That would mean: insurance benefits — health insurance, pension insurance, unemployment insurance, long-term care insurance — are brought together in a uniform Insurance Social Code. Social-assistance benefits — *Bürgergeld*, social assistance, basic income support, student support under the Federal Training Assistance Act, asylum-seeker benefits — are brought together in a Social Assistance Social Code. Public-provision benefits — hospital planning, municipal health care, the territorial component of integration assistance — are brought together in a Public Provision Social Code. Market-related regulations — PKV supervision, supplementary insurance, tariff supervision — are ordered within a corresponding legal framework.

This restructuring would be a generational project of legislative work. It would take years, if not one to two decades. But it would be worthwhile, because it would adapt social law in its structure to the architecture of the four logics — and thus create the precondition for future reforms to take place within a coherent architecture, rather than in an ever-growing layer of hybrid conflations. That such a restructuring of social law oriented to the four logics is not a theoretical construct is shown by the Dutch example: the division there into *Zorgverzekeringswet*, *Wet langdurige zorg* and *Wet maatschappelijke ondersteuning* is at its core precisely such a restructuring of social law along logics rather than along historically grown fields of benefit — and it was realised, as set out in Chapter 5.4, in a sequence of reform steps stretched over more than a decade.

The decisive point of the parallel SGB restructuring is that it does not give up operational care integration but reorganises it on an architecturally clarified basis. The proposal thereby responds to an objection that suggests itself against any architectural clarification: that a clarification of responsibilities could lead to a re-sectorisation in which every actor ‘only does their own thing’ and the patient again experiences breaks in care — this time not because of conflated logics but because of decoupled responsibilities. The thesis advanced here is the reverse: clear architecture is not the opposite of care integration but its precondition. Whoever assigns responsibility clearly in architectural terms can demand accountability for outcomes. Whoever works in conflated logics can formulate outcome responsibility only diffusely — which in the end means that no one bears it. For this reason, architectural clarification does not require the absence of a steering hand but, on the contrary, its explicit naming. The verifiable guarantee of the integrative care approach must not be left to an invisible hand that would arise of its own accord from the mere clarity of responsibilities — it must be institutionalised as an explicit, accountable task. Concretely this means a twofold anchoring:

First, a guarantor body named for each care area — as a rule the municipal or regional level — that is responsible for the seamless interaction of the four logics in the concrete care setting and against which this interaction can be measured.

Second, at the level of the individual patient, the navigator function described in Chapter 4.4, which accompanies the person across the logic boundaries. Architectural clarification thus does not create a responsibility-free space but shifts the steering from a diffuse co-responsibility attributable to no one towards a named, visible and verifiable guarantor responsibility. Only this visibility makes outcome responsibility enforceable.

5.4 International References: the Netherlands and Sweden

The idea of an architecturally clarified welfare-state structure is not hypothetical. Two European neighbours have undertaken architectural clarifications over the past two decades whose results can serve as an empirical reference for the transition path proposed here: the Netherlands, with its three-tier separation *Zorgverzekeringswet* — *Wet langdurige zorg* — *Wet maatschappelijke ondersteuning*, and Sweden, with its regional tax financing of the health system.

The Dutch Model: Zvw, Wlz, Wmo

In 2006, with the *Zorgverzekeringswet* (Zvw), the Netherlands undertook a fundamental restructuring of the health-insurance system.

The Zvw establishes a uniform compulsory health insurance for all residents, whose benefits catalogue is defined by law and whose implementation takes place through privately organised insurers in regulated competition (Schäfer et al., 2010; Kroneman et al., 2016). The insurers compete for insured persons but are obliged to accept applicants and are subject to a strict risk-structure equalisation (Van Kleef, Schut & van de Ven, 2014).

In parallel, long-term care was organised in the *Wet langdurige zorg* (Wlz, in its present form since 2015) as an independent solidarity-based compulsory insurance with an extended social function — it covers those forms of care that, on account of their intensity and duration, are not insurable within the framework of the Zvw (Wammes et al., 2024).

The third pillar is the *Wet maatschappelijke ondersteuning* (Wmo), which organises municipal responsibility for social participation, domestic support and social accompaniment. The Wmo was introduced in 2007 and fundamentally reformed in 2015; it is, in the Dutch architecture, the place at which the social-assistance logic is municipally borne.

The Dutch separation Zvw — Wlz — Wmo corresponds almost exactly to the triad of Insurance — extended insurance with a social function — municipal social assistance. The market logic is located within the Zvw as regulated competition, not as a parallel special structure alongside the solidarity-based insurance.

Over the past nearly two decades this architecture has undergone an empirical test whose results are on the whole positive — for all the detailed problems that such a complex system inevitably brings forth. The Dutch health system held top positions in the Euro Health Consumer Index for several years and was the only country represented continuously in the leading group since the introduction of that index (Kroneman et al., 2016; Wammes et al., 2024); to steer the reformed system, the Netherlands established a comprehensive monitoring instrument as early as 2006 with the Dutch Health Care Performance Report, based on around 125 indicators. The temporal structure of the conversion is also notable, underlining its character as a generational task: the architectural clarification did not proceed as a single act but as a stretched-out sequence — 2006 the restructuring of curative care in the Zvw, 2007 the introduction of the Wmo, 2015 the fundamental reform of long-term care (Wlz) and municipal support (Wmo). Between the first and the architecture-completing reform step there thus lay nearly a decade; the institutional consolidation took considerably longer still.

The Dutch experience shows above all two things: an architectural separation of the four logics is politically and institutionally realisable in a European welfare state of the conservative-corporatist type — and it is a multi-stage process that demands political continuity across legislative terms.

The Swedish Model: Regional Tax Funding

Sweden organises its health system in a fundamentally different architecture from Germany: the main funding takes place through the regional taxes of the 21 regions (*regionkommun*), which are responsible for the provision of health care (Anell, Glenngård & Merkur, 2012; Glenngård, 2024). The central state sets the framework, defines minimum standards and finances a share of health expenditure through allocations — but the operational responsibility lies with the regions.

From the perspective of the Welfare State Matrix, the Swedish model is a highly public-provision-centred system. The territorial responsibility of the regions is not a peripheral supplement to the insurance logic but the load-bearing structural principle. The insurance logic recedes accordingly; insurance elements exist only in specific marginal areas. The social-assistance logic is located at the municipal level (*kommun*) — it bears the social benefits, the domestic care, the social support. The market logic is very weakly developed in the Swedish system (Fredriksson, Eriksson & Tritter, 2008).

The Swedish model is not one-to-one transferable to Germany — the German insurance tradition is too deeply anchored to be replaced by a regionally tax-financed public provision. The Swedish model is, however, instructive, because it shows that a territorial, public-provision-based care architecture functions durably in a European welfare state.

In the international performance comparison of the Commonwealth Fund, the Swedish system regularly performs better than other tax-financed systems at a comparable level of expenditure (measured against gross domestic product); the Healthcare Act of 2017 has moreover anchored a legal entitlement to timely medical assessment and a strengthened interlocking of regional and municipal responsibility (Glenngård, 2024; Anell, Glenngård & Merkur, 2012). It thus supplies an important reference for the question of how the German welfare state could strengthen the public-provision component of its care structure — as an integral part of its architecture, not as a residual repair function at the margin of the insurance logic.

Together, the two international references yield a consistent picture: architectural clarification is possible, it functions in different configurations, and it leads to care systems that are structurally more stable and politically better steerable than today's German hybrid condition. Both systems do, however, generate problems of their own — no model is free of them: the Dutch system is under persistent cost pressure and is among the most expenditure-intensive health systems in the OECD; the Swedish system struggles with regional care disparities, waiting times for elective procedures and staff shortages. These problems are real, but they are of a different nature from the German logic conflation: they are steering and resource problems within a clarified architecture, not structural attribution defects of the architecture itself. They can be addressed without calling the basic structure into question — which is precisely not the case with the German hybrid condition.

For the German discussion, a question of direction thus remains open: whether the target architecture of the German welfare state should follow more the Dutch model of regulated insurance competition or more the Swedish model of regionally anchored public provision. What is meant here is not only the

design of the transition path but the orientation of the target image itself. This question of direction is open for the German discussion — what is decisive, first of all, is that it is posed as an architectural question at all.

6 Research Outlook and Follow-Up Questions

The Welfare State Matrix developed in this paper is a diagnostic tool. It supplies neither a finished reform programme nor does it claim to conclude the analytical work on the architecture of the welfare state — on the contrary: it opens a series of follow-up questions that concern partly the methodological development of the model, partly its empirical grounding and partly its political application. The following sections sketch four lines of inquiry that follow from the diagnosis advanced here — three of them of a scholarly, one of a reform-policy nature.

6.1 Methodological Development

A first line of inquiry concerns the methodological development of the matrix itself. The form presented here is a first, ideal-typical sketch. It can be refined in several directions.

First, through a systematic application to further fields of social benefits beyond the health and long-term care systems — in particular pensions, unemployment insurance, education and family benefits.

Second, through an operationalisation that breaks down individual social benefits quantitatively along their logic components — for instance by quantifying the fiscal volumes per component per field of benefit.

Third, through a comparative application to other European welfare states — in particular to the other representatives of the conservative-corporatist type such as France, Italy and Austria. These countries are not cases in which logic confluences would only be expected in the future; on account of their welfare-state type, related to that of Germany, structurally comparable logic confluences are already manifest today.

A comparative analysis could therefore clarify whether the diagnosis developed here for the German case holds across countries, and which architectural clarifications can be observed or anticipated in these countries.

6.2 Empirical Follow-Up Research

A second line of inquiry concerns empirical research on concrete reform constellations. The matrix can be used to structure the accompanying research on major reform projects — hospital structure reforms, long-term care strengthening acts, the Federal Participation Act, the implementation of the KHVG — along the logic confluences. The guiding question is whether a concrete reform element resolves an existing logic confluence, reproduces it unchanged, or generates a new confluence elsewhere. A systematic working-through of this question would not only ground the model empirically but also supply practical guidance for reform-impact research — and could in the medium term be condensed into an architecture check that examines legislative projects for their architectural consistency already at the draft stage.

6.3 Political Follow-Up Questions

A third line of inquiry concerns the political follow-up discussion. Architectural clarification raises several questions that were only touched on in this paper: what fiscal burden on the federal budget would be associated with a transfer of the *Bürgergeld*–GKV financing into the social-assistance logic, and how could it be made politically negotiable? Which constitutional constructions would be viable for a Welfare State Architecture Act, and what preparatory work would be necessary for it? How could the parallel restructuring of the Social Code be operationally integrated into the legislative process? These questions are highly practical in political terms — and they require a follow-up discussion in that intersection of scholarship, politics and practice in which welfare-state reforms are actually shaped.

6.4 On Urgency: the Reform-Policy Implication of the Diagnosis

A fourth and concluding follow-up question concerns the reform-policy implication of the diagnosis advanced. The model developed in this paper reconstructs the structural cause at which German welfare-state reform has found its limit of effect for several decades. This diagnosis does not necessarily imply a particular speed of reform. But it does imply a statement about the direction of reform:

As long as the logic confluences are not systematically addressed, it is to be expected that future reforms, too, will founder at structurally similar limits of effect as their predecessors.

The architectural diagnosis is not the result of reform-policy considerations but their analytical preliminary question. The deferability of this preliminary question is limited: with every year in which the structural clarification is postponed, both the fiscal follow-on effects of the existing logic confluences and the political and institutional effort of every later clarification strategy grow.

The need for action thus exists not only in a distant future — it exists now. The complete architectural clarification is, to be sure, a generational task; its beginning is not. The first step is not the finished architecture act but a series of measures that can be initiated immediately, with which the transition can be begun in this legislative term.

Concretely, three first steps can be named that together form the entry into an architectural operating model.

First, a time-bound, legally mandated commission for an architectural inventory: an existing institution — for instance the Advisory Council on the Assessment of Developments in the Health Care System — would be tasked with systematically inventorying the logic confluences of the German welfare state, ordering them by fiscal volume and urgency of clarification, and presenting a staged plan of disentanglement. Deliberately, no new advisory body is proposed here: the problem of the German welfare state at this point is not a deficit of knowledge but a deficit of structure, and the establishment of ever new commissions carries the danger of relocating a political decision into committee deliberation rather than taking it. The commission meant here is therefore narrow, time-bound and directed at a concrete deliverable — the staged plan.

Second, the anchoring of an architecture check in the regulatory impact assessment: every new social-policy bill would in future be examined for whether it resolves existing logic breaks, reproduces them

or generates new ones — analogous to the already established sustainability and compliance-cost assessment.

Third, the beginning of the substantive clarification at the most costly and most visible logic break: the *Bürgergeld*–GKV financing, whose structural under-funding is already the subject of a legal action by the GKV-Spitzenverband and at which the architectural question will therefore in any case be politically decided in the near future. None of these three steps requires a constitutional amendment; all three are realisable within the current legislative term.

A serious reform policy will have to be measured by whether it poses this preliminary question explicitly — and by the quality of the answers it develops to it.

This responsibility does not begin in the coming generation but with the actors acting today. The coming generation will have to continue and complete the architectural clarification; it is the present generation that must begin it.

7 Eight Theses on the Architecture of the German Welfare State

This concluding section gathers the line of argument of the paper into eight theses. They are neither an appendix nor a mere repetition, but the sharpened sum of the inquiry: each thesis condenses a result that was developed and substantiated in the preceding chapters — from the four-logics diagnosis (Chapter 3) through the four application cases (Chapter 4) to the transition path (Chapter 5).

In this compressed form the theses serve a double purpose.

First, they serve as touchstones: against them, every social-policy reform decision can be examined for whether it is architecturally consistent.

And second, they are formulated as a basis for discussion — as an express invitation to the scholarly and policy-focused engagement with the architectural perspective proposed here.

I. The German welfare state consists of four structurally distinguishable logics — Insurance, Social Assistance, Public Provision and Market — which in its present configuration are systematically pushed into one another.

II. Where social-assistance tasks are financed through insurance contributions, both logics are damaged in their mode of functioning.

III. The reform exhaustion observable for decades is not primarily a problem of financing, of personnel or of demography, but an architectural one.

IV. Hybrid benefits are not anomalies of assignment but interface phenomena; they require architectural clarification, not definitional dissolution.

V. Architectural clarification does not separate the costs — it separates the responsibilities.

VI. An architecturally clarified welfare-state structure is the precondition of integrated care, not its opposite.

VII. Institutional disentanglement is a cross-generational process. It is not a reform programme of one legislative term but a regulatory project with a precise beginning.

VIII. The architecture is not the result of reform policy but its preliminary question.

Bibliography

The bibliography is reproduced in the language of the sources cited, in line with academic referencing practice for German-language scholarship.

- Anell, A., Glenngård, A. H., & Merkur, S. (2012). Sweden: Health system review. *Health Systems in Transition*, 14(5). European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies.
- Augurzyk, B., Krolop, S., Hollenbach, J., Monsees, D., Pilny, A., & Wuckel, C. (2025). *Krankenhaus Rating Report 2025: Aufbruch aus dem Tal der Tränen*. RWI – Leibniz-Institut für Wirtschaftsforschung & Institute for Healthcare Business.
- Bäcker, G., Naegele, G., & Bispinck, R. (2020). *Sozialpolitik und soziale Lage in Deutschland* (6. Aufl., 2 Bände). Springer VS.
- BKK Dachverband. (2026). Hoher Discount für den Bund bei Versicherungsbeiträgen von Bürgergeldempfängern. Stellungnahme. BKK Dachverband.
- Bundesamt für Soziale Sicherung. (2025). GKV-Schätzerkreis: Schätzergebnis für das Jahr 2026. Pressemitteilung, 15. Oktober 2025. Bonn: BAS.
- Bundesärztekammer. (2023). Positionspapier der Bundesärztekammer zum Regelungsbedarf für investorengetragene Medizinische Versorgungszentren. Berlin: BÄK.
- Bundeskanzleramt Österreich. (2025). EU-Aufbau- und Resilienzplan: Stärkung der Primärversorgung. Bundeskanzleramt der Republik Österreich.
- Bundesministerium für Gesundheit. (2026a). Finanzentwicklung der gesetzlichen Krankenversicherung im 1.–4. Quartal 2025. Pressemitteilung, 10. März 2026. Berlin: BMG.
- Bundesministerium für Gesundheit. (2026b). Referentenentwurf zum GKV-Beitragssatzstabilisierungsgesetz (GKV-BStabG). Bundeskabinettsbeschluss vom 29. April 2026. Berlin: BMG.
- Bundesministerium für Gesundheit und Soziale Sicherung. (2003). *Nachhaltigkeit in der Finanzierung der sozialen Sicherungssysteme: Bericht der Kommission (Rürup-Kommission)*. Berlin: BMGS.
- Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie. (2015). *Das Stabilitäts- und Wachstumsgesetz. Monatsbericht 12-2015*. Berlin: BMWi.
- Bundesrat. (2023). Entschließung des Bundesrates: Schaffung eines MVZ-Regulierungsgesetzes. Antrag der Länder Bayern, Rheinland-Pfalz und Schleswig-Holstein, Bundesratsdrucksache 245/23.
- Bundesrat. (2026). Entschließungsbeschluss zur Krankenversicherung der Bürgergeldbeziehenden. 1061. Sitzung vom 30. Januar 2026.
- Bundesrechnungshof. (2021). *Bemerkungen 2021 zur Haushalts- und Wirtschaftsführung des Bundes — Gesetzliche Rentenversicherung*. Bonn.
- Bundesrechnungshof. (2023). *Bemerkungen 2023 — Bericht zur finanziellen Entwicklung der gesetzlichen Rentenversicherung*. Bonn.
- Bundesrechnungshof. (2025). *Bericht über die finanzielle Entwicklung der gesetzlichen Rentenversicherung und ausgewählte rentenpolitische Vorhaben*. Bonn.
- Bundesverfassungsgericht. (2009). Urteil vom 10. Juni 2009, 1 BvR 706/08 u. a. (PKV-Basistarif). BVerfGE 123, 186.
- Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung. (2012). *Gesundheitspolitik: Vorgeschichte der Reformdebatten*. bpb-Dossier. Bonn: bpb.
- BVMed — Bundesverband Medizintechnologie. (2019). *Krankenhausinvestitionen: Finanzierungskrise und Investitionsstau im deutschen Gesundheitswesen*. Berlin: BVMed.
- BVMed — Bundesverband Medizintechnologie. (2023). *Positionspapier des Aktionsbündnisses Krankenhausreform und Sektorenverbindung (AKS) zur Krankenhausreform — Investitionsfinanzierung*. Berlin: BVMed.

- Charité — Universitätsmedizin Berlin. (2024). Social Prescribing EU — Forschungsprojekt zur Erprobung sozialer Verschreibung in der Primärversorgung. Institut für Allgemeinmedizin der Charité.
- Deutsche Krankenhausgesellschaft. (2025). Bestandsaufnahme zur Krankenhausplanung und Investitionsfinanzierung in den Bundesländern 2024. DKG.
- Deutsche Rentenversicherung Bund. (2024). Nicht beitragsgedeckte Leistungen und Bundeszuschüsse in der allgemeinen Rentenversicherung. Fortschreibung der VDR-Veröffentlichung von 2004. DRV-Heft.
- Deutscher Berufsverband für Pflegeberufe. (2019). DBfK-Umfrage 2019: Berufsausstieg und Wechselgedanken in der Pflege. DBfK Bundesverband.
- Deutscher Bundestag. (2025). Gesetz zur Änderung des Grundgesetzes (Artikel 109, 115, 143h): Reform der Schuldenbremse, Sondervermögen Infrastruktur. Drucksache 20/15096. Berlin: Deutscher Bundestag.
- Deutscher Hausärzteverband. (2025). HÄPPI — Hausärztliches Primärversorgungszentrum, Patientenversorgung Interprofessionell. Modellprojekt Baden-Württemberg, Bayern, Rheinland-Pfalz. Berlin: Deutscher Hausärzteverband.
- Diakonie Deutschland. (2025). Primärversorgung weiterentwickeln. Positionspapier. Evangelisches Werk für Diakonie und Entwicklung.
- Enthoven, A. C. (1988). Theory and practice of managed competition in health care finance. North-Holland.
- Esping-Andersen, G. (1990). The three worlds of welfare capitalism. Polity Press.
- Europäische Kommission. (2011). Mitteilung: Reform der EU-Beihilfevorschriften über Dienstleistungen von allgemeinem wirtschaftlichem Interesse. KOM(2011) 146 endg., 23. März 2011.
- Europäischer Gerichtshof. (2003). Urteil vom 24. Juli 2003, Rechtssache C-280/00 — Altmark Trans GmbH und Regierungspräsidium Magdeburg./ . Nahverkehrsgesellschaft Altmark GmbH. Slg. 2003, I-7747.
- Forsthoff, E. (1938). Die Verwaltung als Leistungsträger. Kohlhammer.
- Fredriksson, M., Eriksson, M., & Tritter, J. Q. (2008). Consequences of a decentralized healthcare governance model: Measuring regional authority support for patient choice in Sweden. *Social Science & Medicine*, 67(8), 1359–1367.
- Geißler, R., & Freier, R. (2025). Kommunalen Finanzreport 2025: Knappe Kassen, große Aufgaben. Bertelsmann Stiftung.
- Gesamtverband der Deutschen Versicherungswirtschaft. (2023). Statistiken zur deutschen Versicherungswirtschaft 2023: Substitutive Krankenvoll- und Pflegepflichtversicherung. Berlin: GDV.
- GKV-Spitzenverband. (2025). Klage gegen die Bundesrepublik Deutschland wegen systematischer Unterfinanzierung der gesundheitlichen Versorgung von gesetzlich versicherten Bürgergeldbeziehenden. Pressemitteilung, 11. September 2025.
- GKV-Spitzenverband, Deutsche Krankenhausgesellschaft & Verband der Privaten Krankenversicherung. (2024). GKV-Spitzenverband, PKV und DKG fordern von Ländern höhere Investitionen in Kliniken. Gemeinsame Pressemitteilung.
- Glenngård, A. H. (2024). International Health Care System Profiles: Sweden. The Commonwealth Fund.
- Hacker, J. S. (2004). Privatizing risk without privatizing the welfare state: The hidden politics of social policy retrenchment in the United States. *American Political Science Review*, 98(2), 243–260.
- Hasselhorn, H.-M., Müller, B. H., & Tackenberg, P. (Hrsg.). (2005). Berufsausstieg bei Pflegepersonal: Arbeitsbedingungen und beabsichtigter Berufsausstieg bei Pflegepersonal in Deutschland und Europa (NEXT-Studie). Schriftenreihe der Bundesanstalt für Arbeitsschutz und Arbeitsmedizin, Übersetzung Ü 15.
- Heintze, C., Borchardt, P., Bühling, P., Härtl, A., Reber, K. C., & Stadtmedizin AG am Institut für Allgemeinmedizin. (2023). Social Prescribing: Soziales Miteinander auf Rezept. *Deutsches Ärzteblatt*, 120(15), A 706–710.
- Hockerts, H. G. (1980). Sozialpolitische Entscheidungen im Nachkriegsdeutschland. Klett-Cotta.

- Hockerts, H. G. (2011). *Der deutsche Sozialstaat: Entfaltung und Gefährdung seit 1945*. Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht.
- IGES Institut. (2016). *Gutachten zur Kostendeckung der Beitragspauschale für Bezieher von Arbeitslosengeld II. Gutachten im Auftrag des Bundesministeriums für Gesundheit*. IGES Institut.
- IGES Institut. (2024). *Aktualisierung des Forschungsgutachtens zur Kostendeckung der Beitragspauschale für Bürgergeldbeziehende — Datenbasis 2022. Gutachten im Auftrag des GKV-Spitzenverbandes*. IGES Institut.
- Kassenärztliche Bundesvereinigung. (2026). *Praxen nicht kaputtsparen — Kampagne*. KBV-Pressemitteilung, Mai 2026.
- Kassenzahnärztliche Bundesvereinigung. (2024). *Fremdinvestoren in der vertragszahnärztlichen Versorgung*. Berlin: KZBV.
- Krankenhausversorgungsverbesserungsgesetz (KHVVVG). (2024). *Bundesgesetzblatt I*.
- Kroneman, M., Boerma, W., van den Berg, M., Groenewegen, P., de Jong, J., & van Ginneken, E. (2016). *The Netherlands: Health system review*. *Health Systems in Transition*, 18(2). European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies.
- Kuhn, J., & Wildner, M. (2020). *Corona-Krise und öffentlicher Gesundheitsdienst*. *Gesundheit und Gesellschaft Wissenschaft (GGW)*, 20(4), 15–22.
- Lauterbach, K. W. (2004). *Bürgerversicherung*. In K. W. Lauterbach & M. Lungen (Hrsg.), *Reform der Krankenversicherung: Bürgerversicherung oder Kopfpauschale?* (S. 11–37). Lit Verlag.
- Lessenich, S. (2012). *Die Neuerfindung des Sozialen: Der Sozialstaat im flexiblen Kapitalismus*. Transcript.
- Marburger Bund. (2025). *MB-Monitor 2024: Ergebnisse der Mitgliederbefragung*. Marburger Bund Bundesverband.
- Max-Planck-Institut für Sozialrecht und Sozialpolitik. (2007). *Die Reform des niederländischen Krankenversicherungssystems*. MPI-Studie.
- Pierson, P. (2000). *Increasing returns, path dependence, and the study of politics*. *American Political Science Review*, 94(2), 251–267.
- PKV-Verband — Verband der Privaten Krankenversicherung. (2025). *Krankenversicherung für Beamtinnen und Beamte*. Köln/Berlin: PKV-Verband.
- PKV-Verband — Verband der Privaten Krankenversicherung. (2026). *PKV-Branchenzahlen 2025: Private Krankenversicherung mit stabilem Wachstum*. Pressemitteilung, 4. Februar 2026. Köln/Berlin: PKV-Verband.
- Pressel, H. (2012). *Der Gesundheitsfonds: Entstehung, Einführung und Weiterentwicklung*. Springer VS.
- Ritter, G. A. (2010). *Der Sozialstaat: Entstehung und Entwicklung im internationalen Vergleich* (3. Aufl.). Oldenbourg.
- Rothgang, H. (2023). *Zur Notwendigkeit einer Finanz- und Strukturreform der Pflegeversicherung*. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt – Gesundheitsforschung – Gesundheitsschutz*, 66(5), 489–497.
- Rothgang, H., & Müller, R. (2024). *BARMER Pflegereport 2024: Pflagerisiko und Pflegedauer*. Schriftenreihe zur Gesundheitsanalyse, Band 47. BARMER.
- Rürup, B. (2003). *Nachhaltigkeit in der Finanzierung der Sozialen Sicherungssysteme: Bericht der Kommission*. Berlin: Bundesministerium für Gesundheit und Soziale Sicherung.
- Rürup, B. (2008). *Umstellung auf eine monistische Finanzierung der Krankenhäuser: Expertise im Auftrag des Bundesministeriums für Gesundheit*. Berlin: BMG.
- Sachße, C., & Tennstedt, F. (1980–2012). *Geschichte der Armenfürsorge in Deutschland* (Bände 1–4). Kohlhammer.
- Sachverständigenrat zur Begutachtung der Entwicklung im Gesundheitswesen. (2018). *Bedarfsgerechte Steuerung der Gesundheitsversorgung*. Gutachten 2018.

- Sachverständigenrat zur Begutachtung der Entwicklung im Gesundheitswesen. (2023). Resilienz im Gesundheitswesen. Gutachten 2023.
- Sachverständigenrat zur Begutachtung der gesamtwirtschaftlichen Entwicklung. (2004). Erfolge im Ausland — Herausforderungen im Inland: Jahresgutachten 2004/05. Wiesbaden: Statistisches Bundesamt.
- Schäfer, W., Kroneman, M., Boerma, W., van den Berg, M., Westert, G., Devillé, W., & van Ginneken, E. (2010). The Netherlands: Health system review. *Health Systems in Transition*, 12(1). European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies.
- Scheuplein, C. (2024). Private-Equity-geführte Praxisketten der ambulanten Versorgung in Deutschland. Stand Dezember 2024. Berlin: VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik.
- Schmähl, W. (2007). Die Einführung der „dynamischen Rente“ 1957: Begründung und langfristige Bedeutung. ZeS-Arbeitspapier 3/2007. Zentrum für Sozialpolitik, Universität Bremen.
- Schmidt, M. G. (2005). Sozialpolitik in Deutschland: Historische Entwicklung und internationaler Vergleich (3. Aufl.). VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften.
- Schröder, H. (2024). Erneuter Rekordwert bei den GKV-Arzneimittelkosten: Anstieg um 74 Prozent in den letzten zehn Jahren. Pressemitteilung des Wissenschaftlichen Instituts der AOK (WIdO), 26. November 2024. Berlin: WIdO.
- Schröter, T. (2024). Primärmedizinische Versorgung in Deutschland am Scheideweg. *Die Innere Medizin*, 65(11), 1042–1051. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00108-024-01757-5>
- Schwabe, U., & Ludwig, W.-D. (Hrsg.). (2023). *Arzneiverordnungs-Report 2023: Aktuelle Daten, Kosten, Trends und Kommentare*. Berlin/Heidelberg: Springer.
- Statistisches Bundesamt. (2024). Grunddaten der Krankenhäuser — Fachserie 12 Reihe 6.1.1. Wiesbaden: Destatis.
- Stelkens, U. (2021). *Recht der Daseinsvorsorge im europäischen Mehrebenensystem*. Lehrmaterialien Universität Speyer.
- Streeck, W., & Thelen, K. (Eds.). (2005). *Beyond continuity: Institutional change in advanced political economies*. Oxford University Press.
- Techniker Krankenkasse. (2026). *Krankenkassenbeiträge und Bürgergeld*. TK-Stellungnahme.
- Tennstedt, F. (1981). *Sozialgeschichte der Sozialversicherung*. Kohlhammer.
- Van Kleef, R., Schut, F., & van de Ven, W. (2014). *Evaluatie Zorgstelsel en Risicoverevening*. Acht Jaar na Invoering Zorgverzekeringswet. Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam.
- ver.di — Vereinte Dienstleistungsgewerkschaft. (2009). *Stellungnahme zur Anhörung des Gesundheitsausschusses des Deutschen Bundestages zum Krankenhausfinanzierungsreformgesetz: Investitionsstau und monistische Finanzierung*. Berlin: ver.di Bundesverwaltung.
- Wammes, J. J. G., Jeurissen, P. P. T., Tanke, M. A. C., Westert, G. P., & van der Wees, P. J. (2024). Healthcare reform in the Netherlands: after 15 years of regulated competition. *Health Economics, Policy and Law*, 19(1), 1–18.
- Wasem, J. (1996). *Eine gesundheitsökonomische Analyse der Privaten Krankenversicherung*. Roderer.
- Weber, M. (1922). *Wirtschaft und Gesellschaft. Grundriss der verstehenden Soziologie*. Mohr Siebeck.
- Wissenschaftliches Institut der AOK (WIdO). (2024). *Der GKV-Arzneimittelmarkt: Klassifikation, Methodik und Ergebnisse 2024*. Berlin: WIdO.

Appendix A — Glossary of Key Terms

The following glossary explains key terms that are used systematically in this paper. It is addressed to readers who are not familiar in all details with the specific terminology of social law and care research.

Welfare State Matrix — The 2x2 classification scheme developed in this paper along the dimensions of financing logic (contribution- versus tax-based) and addressing (collective versus individual). It yields the four ideal types Insurance, Social Assistance, Public Provision and Market.

The Four Logics — The ideal-typical construction principles of welfare-state benefits: Insurance, Social Assistance, Public Provision and Market. Ideal types in the sense of Weberian methodology.

Ideal Type — A methodological construct after Max Weber (1922): the intellectual heightening of certain elements of reality into an internally consistent concept that does not depict reality empirically but serves heuristically for comparison with concrete phenomena.

Logic Break — A point in the welfare-state system at which two or more logics are systematically conflated without their features of responsibility, financing and steering having been architecturally clarified.

Architectural Clarification — The successive dissolution of logic confluations by assigning each component of a social benefit to that logic whose constitutive features correspond to it. The counter-concept to the selective reform of individual logic confluations.

Welfare State Architecture Act — The federal framework proposed in this paper, analogous to the Stability and Growth Act of 1967. It would lay down the definitional separation of the four logics, their financing and responsibility assignment, and a conflict-resolution mechanism for hybrid benefits.

Insurance–Social Assistance Conflation — A type of conflation in which a social-assistance task of the political community is financed from the contribution pool of social insurance. Typical example: the flat-rate contribution for *Bürgergeld* recipients in the GKV.

Insurance–Public Provision Conflation — A type of conflation in which the territorial capacity structure of a care infrastructure is compensated from insurance financing, without the insurance side controlling the investment decision. Typical example: the dual hospital financing, with a de facto GKV subsidisation of the Länder investment gap.

Market–Insurance Conflation — A type of conflation in which market-based and solidarity-based insurance are separated from one another by a rigid portfolio boundary, without a coherent interface architecture being established. Typical example: the German PKV–GKV separation, with systematic risk selection.

Institutional Disentanglement — The term used in this paper for the successive, sequential and asymmetric process in which overlapping welfare-state functional areas are reorganised so that each component is unambiguously assigned to one of the four logics. It connects to institutionalist research on institutional change (Pierson, 2000; Streeck & Thelen, 2005; Hacker, 2004).

Zorgverzekeringswet (Zvw) — The Dutch Health Insurance Act of 2006. It establishes a uniform compulsory health insurance for all residents, with a legally defined benefits catalogue and a privately organised, regulated implementation in competition.

Wet langdurige zorg (Wlz) — The Dutch Long-Term Care Act, in its present form since 2015. It organises intensive long-term care as an independent solidarity-based compulsory insurance with an extended social function.

Wet maatschappelijke ondersteuning (Wmo) — The Dutch Act on Social Support, introduced in 2007, in its present form since 2015. It organises municipal responsibility for social participation, domestic support and social accompaniment. In the Dutch model it corresponds to the social-assistance logic.

Primary-Care Unit (PVE) — The Austrian model of multi-professional, local primary care, established since 2015; strongly expanded since 2022 with EU Recovery and Resilience Plan resources. In July 2025 the hundredth PVE was opened.

Self-Government — The form of organisation established in German social insurance, in which the carriers (sickness funds, pension-insurance carriers and the like) are organised as corporations under public law subject to state supervision and regulate their affairs largely on their own responsibility. It represents the contributors — not the general public.

Flat-Rate Contribution — A flat-rate amount set by the federal government with which the health-insurance contributions for *Bürgergeld* recipients and other recipients of social benefits are settled with the sickness funds. For years it has been structurally below the actual costs of care.

Capacity Funding — A financing component that remunerates the structural securing of the existence of a care institution — for instance a hospital — irrespective of the number of cases actually treated. Architecturally a public-provision function; in Germany it has in effect been relocated into GKV financing by the dual hospital financing of 1972.

Appendix B — About the Author

Prof. Dr. med. Udo Janßen

Physician, economist, business lawyer and university lecturer. His work centres on the interface of care practice, welfare-state analysis and higher-education research.

Current Position

Managing Director of KyberMedis GmbH (Berlin). Founder of the Janssen Consulting Group (2020) — advising municipal carriers, hospitals, social institutions and care structures on strategy and organisational development, restructuring and care architecture.

Academic Education

Studied human medicine (Bonn, Munich). Doctorate (Dr. med., Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich, 1998). Specialist training in gynaecology and obstetrics. Further qualifications: gerontologist, Master of Business Administration, business lawyer, and Master in Work and Organisational Psychology.

Professorships and Teaching

Professor of General Business Administration with a focus on Health Care Management, FOM University of Applied Sciences for Economics and Management (Essen, 2011–2021). Professor of Health Management, IU International University of Applied Sciences (Augsburg, since October 2024). Teaching assignments include the University of Europe for Applied Sciences (Iserlohn, MBA Health Care Management), Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf (Public Health) and the Vienna University of Economics and Business (corporate management in health care). Visiting professorship at Shandong Agricultural University, Tai'an (People's Republic of China).

Earlier Positions

Managing member of the executive board of the German Hospital Institute (DKI) and advisory member of the executive board of the German Hospital Federation (DKG). Director-General (CEO) of the Vienna Hospital Association — today the Vienna Health Association — from 2014 to 2017, with a substantial role in the development and implementation of the Vienna Hospital Concept 2030. Partner Advisory Health Care, KPMG AG Wirtschaftsprüfungsgesellschaft Germany (2018–2021). Partner Health Care and Life Science, Deloitte Germany (until 2024).

Research Focuses and Publications

The architecture of regional care networks; the structural analysis of the German welfare state; the transformation of complex sponsorship structures in health and social care. Founder, editor and co-author of a fourteen-volume textbook series on health and hospital management (Verlag W. Kohlhammer). Author of further monographs and specialist contributions on direct contracts with sickness funds and on medical care centres.

Declaration of Interests

The author is himself active, as Managing Director of KyberMedis GmbH (Berlin), in the field of municipal care architecture, in particular in the planning and support of medical care centres and primary-care centres in municipal sponsorship. The architectural diagnosis developed in this paper thus touches a field of application in which the author is at the same time operationally active as a consultant. The analytical argument of the paper is conceived independently of this; it takes no side for any specific form of sponsorship and makes the conflict of interest expressly transparent here for reasons of scholarly transparency.